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**Performance Analysis of Extension of 3- and 5-bit Quantum
Repetition Codes**

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CANDIDATES' DECLARATION

This is to certify that the work presented in this thesis, titled, "Performance Analysis of Extension of 3- and 5-bit Quantum Repetition Codes", is the outcome of the investigation and research carried out by us under the supervision of Dr Md Saifur Rahman.

It is also declared that neither this thesis nor any part thereof has been submitted anywhere else for the award of any degree, diploma or other qualifications.

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CERTIFICATION

This thesis titled, “**Performance Analysis of Extension of 3- and 5-bit Quantum Repetition Codes**”, submitted by the group as mentioned below has been accepted as satisfactory in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree B.Sc. in EEE in March 2025.

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Contents

<i>CANDIDATES' DECLARATION</i>	i
<i>CERTIFICATION</i>	ii
<i>ACKNOWLEDGEMENT</i>	iii
List of Figures	vii
List of Tables	viii
<i>ABSTRACT</i>	ix
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Quantum Error Correction	1
1.2 Literature Review of the Existing Work	2
1.3 Our Work and its Motivation	4
1.4 Contribution of our work	4
1.5 Organization of the thesis	4
2 Background Theory	5
2.1 Mathematical Background	5
2.1.1 Vectors and Vector Spaces	5
2.1.2 From vector spaces to Hilbert spaces	7
2.1.3 Orthogonality, Orthonormality and the Gram-Schmidt process	10
2.1.4 Linear Transformations and Matrices	12
2.1.5 Eigenvalues, eigenvectors and change of basis	14
2.1.6 Properties of Hermitian and Unitary Operators	16
2.1.7 Dual Spaces, Braket Notation and the Projection Operator	17
2.1.8 Tensor product of matrices and vectors	19
2.2 Background for Quantum Computation and Quantum Error Correction	19
2.2.1 Quantum States, Observables, Measurement, Dynamics and Assembly	19
2.2.2 Qubits and Quantum Gates	22
2.2.3 Pure and Mixed States, Density operator and the Krauss operator	29
2.3 Quantum Information and Error Correction	31

3	Introduction to Quantum Error Correction	33
3.1	GHZ state	33
3.2	Quantum Error Correcting (QEC) Codes	34
3.2.1	Performance Evaluation	35
3.3	Quantum Repetition Code (QRC)	36
3.4	Three bit QRC	39
3.4.1	Using the Extra State bits in Syndrome Measurement	41
3.4.2	Correcting Phase Flip Errors	41
3.4.3	Fidelity Calculation	42
3.5	Five bit QRC	43
3.5.1	Comparison with the 3-bit QRC	44
3.6	Performance Analysis of QRC	44
4	Design and Simulation of the Proposed Extension of 3- and 5-bit QRC Codes	46
4.1	Design of Quantum Circuits	46
4.2	Simulation of Quantum Circuits	47
4.3	Extension of Three-bit QRC on Tripartite GHZ State	47
4.3.1	Decoding Circuit	47
4.3.2	Design of the Complete Circuit	48
4.4	Extension of Five-bit QRC on Tripartite GHZ State	49
4.5	Extension of Three-bit QRC on Pentapartite GHZ State	51
4.5.1	The Decoding Circuit	51
4.5.2	Design of the Complete Circuit	53
4.6	Extension of Five-bit QRC on Pentapartite GHZ State	55
5	Results and Discussion	57
5.1	Fidelity of an Ideal GHZ state	57
5.1.1	Simulation Method	57
5.1.2	Simulation Results	58
5.2	Fidelity of the Generalized GHZ States	59
5.2.1	For Extended 3-bit QRC on Tripartite GHZ states	60
5.2.2	For an Extended 5-bit QRC on Tripartite GHZ states	61
5.2.3	For an Extended 3-bit QRC on Pentapartite GHZ states	62
5.2.4	For an Extended 5-bit QRC on Pentapartite GHZ states	63
5.2.5	Comparison of Results	64
6	Conclusions and Future Work	69
6.1	Conclusions	69
6.2	Contributions and Novelty	69
6.3	Suggestions for Future Work	70

References	71
A Codes	76
A.1 Design of Error-correcting Schemes	76
A.1.1 Extended 3-bit QRC on Tripartite GHZ state	76
A.1.2 Extended 5-bit QRC on Tripartite GHZ state	78
A.1.3 Extended 3-bit QRC on Pentapartite GHZ state	80
A.1.4 Extended 5-bit QRC on Pentapartite GHZ state	84
A.2 Simulation of Extended 3-bit QRC on an Ideal Tripartite GHZ state	88

List of Figures

2.1	Relationship between the various spaces	10
2.2	Bloch sphere	24
3.1	A basic quantum error-correcting scheme ¹	34
3.2	Detecting errors for the 3-bit bit-flip error correction code. The bottom two ancilla bits are measured to detect a single bit-flip error in the top three bits. The circuit is called a syndrome extraction circuit	39
3.3	3-bit QRC on a single state	40
3.4	3-bit QRC on a single state without extra ancillary bits	41
3.5	Encoding circuit for the 3-bit phase flip error code	42
3.6	5-bit QRC on a single state	43
3.7	Efficacy of Quantum Repetition Codes	45
4.1	Syndrome Extraction and Correction Circuit for tripartite GHZ state	48
4.2	3-bit QRC on a tripartite generalized GHZ state (the bottom part is the continuation of the first part to the right)	49
4.3	5-bit QRC on a tripartite generalized GHZ state (the bottom part is the continuation of the first part to the right)	50
4.4	Syndrome Extraction and Correction Circuit for pentapartite generalized GHZ state (each subsequent part after the first is the continuation of the first part to the right)	52
4.5	3-bit QRC on a pentapartite generalized GHZ state (each subsequent part after the first is the continuation of the first part to the right)	54
4.6	5-bit QRC on a pentapartite generalized GHZ state (each subsequent part after the first is the continuation of the first part to the right)	56
5.1	Circuit Digram for simulation of a 3-bit QRC on a tripartite ideal GHZ state	58
5.2	Approximate Fidelity of a tripartite ideal GHZ state	59
5.3	Comparison of a traditional 3-bit QRC from single state to pentapartite GHZ state	64
5.4	Comparison of a traditional 5-bit QRC from single state to pentapartite GHZ state	65
5.5	Comparison of an extended 3-bit QRC with best traditional scheme	66
5.6	Comparison of an extended 5-bit QRC with best traditional scheme	67
5.7	Comparison of all proposed schemes with traditional 3-bit and 5-bit QRC	68

List of Tables

2.1	Comparison between state vector and density operator formalism	30
3.1	Syndrome computation table for a Bit-flip Error (Figure 3.3) ²	39
3.2	Syndrome computation table for a Bit-flip Error (Figure 3.4)	41
3.3	Performance of the 3-bit QRC	43
3.4	Performance of the 5-qubit repetition code ³	43
5.1	Performance of the 3-bit QRC on tripartite GHZ states	60
5.2	Performance of the 5-bit QRC on tripartite GHZ states	61
5.3	Performance of the 3-bit QRC on pentapartite GHZ states	62
5.4	Performance of the 5-bit QRC on pentapartite GHZ states	63

ABSTRACT

Quantum computers are becoming an engineer's reality from a physicist's dream. Microsoft, IBM, Google are some of the key players who are pushing the quantum boundaries and bringing us closer to actual quantum computers. Although research in Quantum Computing is focused mostly on creating viable Qubits, a large portion of research is also dedicated to reducing errors due to decoherence, noise and errors from various sources so that the calculations done using Qubits are not flawed. Transmitting Quantum Information from one place to another is what Quantum Communication is about. Here too, the channel induces errors in the transmitted Qubits leading to loss in quantum information. Quantum Error Correction came as an analogue to classical error correction to solve the same problems of bit errors in quantum computation and communication. This work investigates a type of error correction code, the repetition code, common to both classical and quantum domain. In this work, extended 3-bit and 5-bit quantum repetition codes (QRC) in tripartite and pentapartite GHZ states were investigated to probe their efficacy in error correction. 3- and 5-bit QRC can completely protect the Ideal GHZ state, i.e. resulting fidelity remains at one at all conditions. The research indicates that, in case of generalized GHZ states, all of them performed better than their conventional counterparts, especially extension of 5-bit QRC showing the highest fidelity. Modified 5 bit quantum repetition code in pentapartite GHZ state displayed a fidelity margin of 0.075-0.1 over traditional 3-bit QRC on a single state. However small this margin may seem, this fidelity increase is quite remarkable in large-scale quantum computations and practical implementations.

Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter will give an introductory view on quantum error correction, its motivation along with a review of the existing work. It will also present the contributions of the research and the organization of the thesis.

1.1 Quantum Error Correction

Quantum Computation and Artificial Intelligence are the two technologies that hold the most promise to revolutionize our future. Although much theoretical and practical advancements have been achieved in the field of AI, ML and DL, quantum computation has yet to see a viable commercial large-scale operation. Like AI, growth in the QC landscape was prohibited by the technology of the time. But with the creation of several large-scale quantum computers [1] this field is seeing an influx of new research. Much research has already been done, most of it is directed towards the physical realization of qubits. Topological qubits [2] and superconducting qubits [3] are two of the most promising leads in this direction. However, even if physical qubits are viably realized, the problem of protecting the qubits remains.

Qubits remain in quantum superposition of its two possible measurable states and this quantum allows it to achieve things that are not possible by classical computers. As a simple example, the superposition allows a collection of qubits to undergo the same operation in parallel as seen in Shor's factorization algorithm [4], something that would require an exponentially large number of classical bits. Interaction with the environment may result in an unwanted loss of the phase and amplitude information contained in the superposition due to the unwanted interference of the environment wavefunction. This is known as decoherence. Noise and unwanted measurement also pose a threat to the quantum information stored in a qubit as unwanted measurement can convert it from a quantum superposition to a classical probabilistic pbit [5]. In other words, the pure state gets transformed into a mixed state. Decoherence is also an obstacle in send-

ing Quantum Information from one location to another, that is, Quantum Communication. The channel induces errors in the transmitted qubits leading to a decrease in fidelity. Quantum Error Correction (QEC) addresses this fragility of qubits. Unlike classical error correction which uses redundancy to protect the bits [6], QEC harnesses the properties unique to qubits, superposition and entanglement, to protect the information stored in them. Quantum Repetition Code (QRC), Stabilizer Codes [7] [8], Low Density Parity Check (LDPC) codes and Fault Tolerant Codes [9] are among the most popular types of QEC codes.

1.2 Literature Review of the Existing Work

The field of Quantum Error Correction (QEC) has seen a lot of research and the work has sprung in different directions. Since qubits are quite prone to environmental effects, it becomes quite necessary to protect the qubits. When left to itself, qubits will evolve unitarily with time [10], and as such, pure quantum states will remain pure. But practically qubits must go through physical realization, i.e. the circuit will have to be kept in an environment. Hence, a loose coupling of the system and the environment exists, represented using the Kraus operator [11], causing some information to be lost to the environment from the system. This is known as decoherence. Due to the environment-system interference, the system's time evolution when observed alone seems to be non-unitary, although the environment-system evolves unitarily [12]. It has been shown that decoherence is equivalent to quantum entanglement [13]. The problem of decoherence along with noise and unwanted measurement are inherent to any quantum system dedicated to quantum computation or communication. Various methods exist for combating these problems, but one of the most powerful tools against it is Quantum Error Correction.

Quantum Repetition Code (QRC) is the simplest form of QEC scheme. It simply means sending the same qubit multiple times, that is, sending $|\psi \dots \psi\rangle$ instead of $|\psi\rangle$. Such simple codes provide much protection against bit flip errors but fail to reduce phase flip errors appreciably. If a Quantum Error Correcting Code (QECC) can correct both bit flip and phase flip errors, then it can correct any arbitrary single qubit errors [10]. Although it was first thought that repetition codes would not be viable for qubits due to the no-cloning theorem [14], P. Shor proved this naive belief to be wrong by providing an example of a QEC code that provided protection against phase flip too, Shor's 9-qubit code [15]. Repetition codes are especially effective in protecting qubits with equiprobable states with same phase, providing fidelity 1 in all cases. Repetition codes applied to such states create Bell states or the ideal GHZ states [16], that give fidelity 1 for any probability of bit flip error [17].

Sparsity in data has encouraged research into sparsity-utilizing methods for data reconstruction, Compressed Sensing [18] being a result of such excursion. Sparsity was also seen as an encouragement for creating Low-Density Parity Codes or LDPC codes in short, which were

originally developed for classical error correction [19]. After research into QEC boomed, they were extended to be used for QEC [20]. Quantum LDPC (QLDPC) codes make use of sparse parity-check matrices to encode quantum information, thus reducing the overhead associated with traditional QEC methods. Despite such theoretical advantages, practical implementation remains unfeasible due to the complexity of syndrome decoding in quantum systems.

Another extension of the classical codes to the QEC is the Stabilizer Code, which shows much promise. It is the generalization of classical linear codes to the quantum domain. As proposed by Gottesman [7], these codes use stabilizer sets, operators that leave any specific qubit unchanged to explain error correction. The connection between linear spaces over finite fields and QEC codes studied in [21] [22] led to the connection between classical EC and QEC. The 7-qubit Steane code [23], Calderbank-Shor-Steane (CSS) code [21] are notable examples of stabilizer codes. Surface codes or toric codes are another promising example seeing much research in recent times that uses the formalism of stabilizer codes [24], although it is a form of topological QEC code. Google's Sycamore processor used distance-5 surface codes for error correction, making it major milestone in practical QEC [25]. A new variant of the surface code, the XZZX code has shown improvement in handling biased-noise with dephasing found in superconducting qubits [26]. Bosonic codes are a recent area of research in the field of QEC that uses continuous variable quantum states rather than discrete ones, usually in oscillators. The Gottesman-Kitaev-Preskill (GKP) codes [27] use squeezed states while cat codes [28] use superposition of coherent states to protect against errors. The advantage of these codes is reduction in overhead resources.

In a fascinating development creating an exchange of knowledge between the fields of AI and QC, neural networks [29], Reinforcement Learning [30] and Deep Learning [31] were used for decoding and optimizing QEC codes. The connection between classical and quantum EC was exploited to extend to nonbinary QEC [32] [33]. Quantum entanglement can be used to transmit quantum information [34] [35], and it was shown that this could be used to create EC codes, called Entanglement-Assisted Quantum Error Correction Code (EAQECC) [36]. Use of such entanglement along with Quantum Repetition code also leads improvement in fidelity as studied in [37] [38], from which our work takes some inspiration.

Fault-tolerant QEC is another scheme of QEC that ensures that errors do not spread uncontrollably during quantum computation. Fault Tolerant Quantum Computation (FTQC) can perform computation on codewords without decoding them to their original information, making it very important for large-scale quantum computing [9]. Various techniques such as transversal gates, magic state distillation, and concatenated codes allow for reliable computation even in the presence of noise. Threshold theorems indicate that if the physical error rate is below a certain threshold, fault-tolerant architectures can suppress errors arbitrarily well [39].

QEC is of utmost importance for sustainable and reliable quantum computing. QEC and sta-

bilizer codes provide the foundation for fault-tolerant and surface codes which might be better suited for practical implementation. Although QRC is quite simple, it still proves to be effective in many cases, although proper practicality can only be judged when viable methods exist for reliable operation of a significant amount of qubits in a quantum computer.

1.3 Our Work and its Motivation

Our work focuses on 3-bit and 5-bit Quantum Repetition Codes. More precisely, extensions of these codes on tri- and pentapartite GHZ states were proposed, and their performance was analyzed. Modifications were mostly done on the decoding part of the circuit. We found their fidelity to be better than their existing counterparts. The work was motivated by the recent work on Repetition Codes by Shubha et al [37] [38].

1.4 Contribution of our work

The main contributions of our work are:

- Extension and performance analysis of the three bit Quantum Repetition Code to tripartite and pentapartite GHZ states
- Extension and performance analysis of the five bit Quantum Repetition Code to tripartite and pentapartite GHZ states
- Comparison of fidelity of these extended codes with existing codes

1.5 Organization of the thesis

The rest of the thesis is organized as follows:

Chapter 2 goes over some of the mathematical and quantum background material required for understanding the rest of the thesis

Chapter 3 explains the specific material on which our work is done along with the methods used

Chapter 4 contains our contribution with design, simulation and explanations

Chapter 5 contains the results of our experimentation and its discussion

Chapter 6 concludes the thesis and speculates on the direction of future work

Chapter 2

Background Theory

This chapter describes the necessary background theory to comprehend and explore the underlying problems and error correction techniques in Quantum Computation and Communication.

2.1 Mathematical Background

2.1.1 Vectors and Vector Spaces

Quantum mechanics and, by extension, Quantum Computing use a lot of mathematical machinery, most of which is linear algebra and some functional analysis. Since computers cannot handle infinity, quantum computing is limited to the linear algebra of finite dimensions. The following consists of some mathematical definitions, theorems and lemmas required for understanding the material presented in this thesis. The reader is referred to [40] [41] [10] [42] [43] for covering these in more depth.

Definition 1. A **field** is a set F with two operations defined on it: $+$ (addition) and \cdot (multiplication) such that the following properties hold $\forall a, b, c \in F$.

1. $a + b = b + a$ and $a \cdot b = b \cdot a$
2. $(a + b) + c = a + (b + c)$ and $(a \cdot b) \cdot c = a \cdot (b \cdot c)$
3. $\exists 0, 1 \in F$ such that $a + 0 = 0 + a = a$ and $a \cdot 1 = 1 \cdot a = a$
4. $\forall a \in F, \exists (-a) \in F$ such that $a + (-a) = (-a) + a = 0$, and, $\forall a \in F, \exists a^{-1} \in F$ such that $a \cdot a^{-1} = a^{-1} \cdot a = 1$
5. $a \cdot (b + c) = a \cdot b + a \cdot c$

The \cdot sign for multiplication is usually suppressed and written as $a.b = ab$ [44]. The set of real numbers and complex numbers are examples of fields.

Definition 2. A **vector space** V over a field F (whose elements are called **scalars**) is a set of elements, called **vectors**, with the operations of vector addition between vectors and scalar multiplication between a scalar and a vector defined on them satisfying the following axioms (called the vector space axioms) for any $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \in V$ and $a, b \in F$:

1. $a\mathbf{u} + b\mathbf{v} = b\mathbf{v} + a\mathbf{u} \in V$
2. $(ab)\mathbf{u} = a(b\mathbf{u})$
3. $(\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{v}) + \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{u} + (\mathbf{v} + \mathbf{w})$
4. $(a + b)\mathbf{u} = a\mathbf{u} + b\mathbf{u}$ and $a(\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{v}) = a\mathbf{u} + a\mathbf{v}$
5. $\exists \mathbf{0} \in V$ such that $\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{0} = \mathbf{0} + \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}$
6. $\exists 1 \in F$ such that $1\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}$
7. $\forall \mathbf{u} \in V, \exists (-\mathbf{u})$ such that $\mathbf{u} + (-\mathbf{u}) = (-\mathbf{u}) + \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}$

Real numbers, complex numbers, polynomials with complex(or real) coefficients of degree upto some fixed number, lists of complex (or real) numbers with elementwise addition and multiplication defined on them (denoted as \mathbb{C}^n or \mathbb{R}^n) – all are examples of vector spaces over the field of real (or complex for some) numbers [44] [45].

From here on, all definitions assume V as a vector space over the field F . Furthermore, a vector space for which the field is the set of real numbers \mathbb{R} is called a **real vector space**. Similarly, a vector space for which the field is the set of complex numbers \mathbb{C} is called a **complex vector space** [44].

Definition 3. A **linear combination** of a set of vectors $\{\mathbf{u}_i \in V \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is a weighted sum of these vectors with some scalars, that is, $\sum_{i=1}^n a_i \mathbf{u}_i$, where $a_i \in F, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Definition 4. The **span** of a set of vectors $\{\mathbf{u}_i \in V \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is the set of all vectors that can be formed by linear combinations of vectors in this set, $\mathbf{u} = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \mathbf{u}_i$ for all possible values of the scalars $\{a_i \in F \mid i = 1, \dots, n\}$.

Definition 5. A set of vectors $\{\mathbf{u}_i \in V \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is said to be **linearly independent** if none of them can be written as a linear combination of the other vectors.

Theorem 1. A set of vectors $\{\mathbf{u}_i \in V \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is linearly independent if and only if $\sum_{i=1}^n a_i \mathbf{u}_i = \mathbf{0}$ is true only for $a_i = 0, \forall i = 1, \dots, n$.

Definition 6. A **basis** of a vector space V is a set of linearly independent vectors $\{\mathbf{e}_i \mid i = 1, 2, \dots\}$ that spans the whole space. Each vector in the basis is called a basis vector.

A vector space can be spanned by different sets of basis vectors (or different bases).

Theorem 2. *Every basis of a vector space contains the same number of vectors.*

Definition 7. The **dimension** of a vector space V is the least number of linearly independent vectors required to span the whole space, denoted by $\dim(V)$. In other words, this is the number of basis vectors of a vector space.

Thus, any vector in a vector space can be written as a linear combination of its basis vectors, $\mathbf{u} = \sum_i a_i \mathbf{e}_i$, $a_i \in F$, and the coefficients of each basis vector in such a linear combination is called the **component** of the vector corresponding to that basis vector¹. Thus a_i is the component of \mathbf{u} along the basis vector \mathbf{e}_i . A vector expressed in this way can also be written as a column matrix of the components of corresponding bases given that the choice of bases is known,

$$\mathbf{a} = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ a_n \end{bmatrix}_{n \times 1} \quad (2.1)$$

This form is called the **column vector representation** of a vector for a particular choice of bases. The number of components can be finite or infinite, depending upon the dimension of the vector space. It is to be noted that the choice of basis vectors is not unique and different sets of bases (plural of basis) can be well-suited for different tasks.

2.1.2 From vector spaces to Hilbert spaces

Till now, no concept of distance between vectors, similarity between them or lengths of vectors have been defined. In fact, vector spaces are much more general and can be studied without being endowed with these properties. But the addition of these properties leads to much more fascinating spaces in which we have practical interest.²

Metric and Metric spaces

Definition 8. A **metric** (also called a distance function) is a binary function $d : V \times V \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ defined on a (topological) set X such that for any $x, y, z \in X$,

¹Components are defined again using inner products in the next subsection

²A **space** is any set of elements having some properties. The name of the space depends on the properties of the elements

1. $d(x, y) = d(y, x)$
2. $d(x, x) = 0$
3. $d(x, y) \leq d(x, z) + d(z, y)$

Definition 9. A **metric space** (X, d) is a topological space X with a metric $d : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined on it.

Definition 10. A **metric vector space** (V, d) is a metric space with a metric d whose elements satisfy the vector space axioms.

Normed vector spaces

Definition 11. A **norm** (better known as the length of a vector) is a function $\|\cdot\| : V \mapsto \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ defined on a metric vector space V such that for any $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in V$ and $a \in F$,

1. $\|\mathbf{u}\| \geq 0$
2. $\|a\mathbf{u}\| = |a| \cdot \|\mathbf{u}\|$
3. $\|\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{v}\| \leq \|\mathbf{u}\| + \|\mathbf{v}\|$

We can define a metric from a norm, by defining the metric as $d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}\|$. This is then called a **metric induced by the norm**.

Definition 12. A **normed vector space** is a metric vector space with a norm defined on it. The metric might or might not be induced by the norm.

Inner Product Spaces

Definition 13. An **inner product** is a binary function $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle : V \times V \mapsto F$ defined on a normed vector space V such that for any $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \in V$ and $a, b \in F$,

1. $\langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle = \langle \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u} \rangle^*$, where $*$ denotes complex conjugation
2. $\langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u} \rangle \geq 0$ where equality occurs only when $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}$
3. $\langle a\mathbf{u} + b\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \rangle = a^* \langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w} \rangle + b^* \langle \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \rangle$ ³

An inner product measures the similarity between two vectors. A norm can be defined using the inner product of a vector with itself as, $\|\mathbf{u}\| = \sqrt{\langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u} \rangle}$. This norm is called the **norm induced by the inner product**.

³An alternative to this is: $\langle \mathbf{w}, a\mathbf{u} + b\mathbf{v} \rangle = a^* \langle \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{u} \rangle + b^* \langle \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{v} \rangle$, that is, conjugate linear in the second argument

Definition 14. An **inner product space** is a normed vector space with an inner product defined on it. The norm might or might not be induced by the inner product.

In an inner product space, the "similarity" between vectors can also be measured by defining the cosine of the angle θ between them as,

$$\cos\theta = \frac{|\langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle|}{\sqrt{\langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u} \rangle \langle \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{v} \rangle}} \quad (2.2)$$

which is proven to be well-defined by the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality [41].

Completeness, Banach Spaces and Hilbert Spaces

Definition 15. An infinite sequence (x_n) where each $a_i \in X$ is said to be **Cauchy** if for any real $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a natural number N such that for all $n, m > N$, $d(a_n, a_m) < \varepsilon$, where d is a metric defined on the metric space X .

Theorem 3. *Every Cauchy sequence is convergent*

Definition 16. A set is said to be **complete** when every Cauchy sequence in the set converges to a limit within the set.

Definition 17. A **Banach space** is a complete normed vector space.

At this point, we can define an example of a Banach space and its relevant terminology which is of utmost importance in our current study. First, we define its norm ubiquitous in mathematics and physics.

Definition 18. The ℓ_p norm of a vector \mathbf{u} is defined as $\|\mathbf{u}\|_p = \sqrt[p]{\sum_i |u_i|^p}$ for $p \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, where u_i is the i -th component of the vector and the upper limit of the summation might be finite or infinite depending on the vector space.

Definition 19. An ℓ_p space is a vector space of sequences of real or complex entries having finite ℓ_p norm.

ℓ_p spaces are examples of Banach spaces. Note that the ℓ_p space has a norm and a norm-induced metric defined on it.

Theorem 4. *All ℓ_p spaces are complete, hence Banach spaces.*

It is noteworthy that finite sequences of real or complex numbers will always have finite ℓ_p norm⁴ and hence form ℓ_p spaces. In finite-dimensional vector spaces, the vectors can be written as a list of components in any basis, where the list of components is a sequence of real or complex numbers. So, all finite-dimensional vector spaces are also ℓ_p spaces.

⁴Here, it is assumed that all the elements of the sequence are defined and finite real or complex numbers

Definition 20. A **Hilbert space** \mathcal{H} is a complete inner product space.

The set of all Hilbert spaces form a subset of the set of all Banach spaces⁵. Among all the ℓ_p spaces, an inner product can be defined on the ℓ_2 space. Hence the ℓ_2 space is a Hilbert space of much importance to us, since all of quantum computing is done on this space⁶.

Vector spaces (and also Hilbert spaces) can have finite or infinite dimensions. But we are concerned only with finite-dimensional vector spaces and so a particular theorem regarding them is especially useful. Figure 2.1 shows the relationship between the various spaces.

Theorem 5. All finite-dimensional inner product spaces are complete, hence (finite-dimensional) Hilbert spaces.

Figure 2.1: Relationship between the various spaces

2.1.3 Orthogonality, Orthonormality and the Gram-Schmidt process

To make our task easier, we define the Kronecker delta as,

$$\delta_i^j = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i = j \\ 0, & \text{if } i \neq j \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

The vector space F^n where $F = \mathbb{C}$ or \mathbb{R} will be of much importance. Its elements are finite sequences of length n , $\mathbf{a} = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ where $a_i \in F, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and a_i is called the i th component of \mathbf{a} in the standard basis. They can also be represented as a column vector of size

⁵It is not required for a Banach space to have an inner product defined on it, it only requires to be complete and normed

⁶Wavefunctions in quantum mechanics are elements of the L^2 Hilbert space. A one-one correspondence between elements of the ℓ_2 space and the L^2 space exists according to the Riesz-Fischer theorem [41]

$n \times 1$,

$$\mathbf{a} = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ a_n \end{bmatrix}_{n \times 1} \quad (2.4)$$

Vector addition and scalar multiplication are defined as for matrices. The set of standard basis vectors is defined as the set of vectors $\{\mathbf{e}_i \mid i = 1, \dots, n\}$ that span this space consisting of vectors having 1 in one position and zero in all others, that is, components of \mathbf{e}_i , $a_j = \delta_i^j$. More explicitly,

$$\mathbf{e}_i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ 1 \text{ (ith row)} \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}_{n \times 1} \quad (2.5)$$

We define the inner product for this space to be $\langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i^* b_i$. It can be easily verified that this induces a norm which in turn induces a metric on this vector space. For $F = \mathbb{R}$ this vector space is called the **n-dimensional Euclidean space** and for $F = \mathbb{C}$ it is called the **n-dimensional Unitary space** [45]. Thus, F^n is now a Hilbert space. Furthermore, its induced norm is actually the ℓ_2 norm, thus, F^n is actually a finite-dimensional ℓ_2 space.

When working in an inner product space, we can define the notion of "perpendicular"ness between vectors using inner products and also use this to find a set of basis vectors perpendicular or orthogonal to each other. Working with a set of orthonormal basis vectors simplifies much of the task.

Definition 21. Two vectors in an inner product space are said to be **orthogonal** if their inner product is zero. A **mutually orthogonal set** of vectors is a set of vectors $\{\mathbf{u}_i \in V \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ that are orthogonal to each other, that is, $\langle \mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{u}_j \rangle = 0$ if $i \neq j$ and not equal to zero when $i = j$.

Definition 22. A **unit vector** is a vector whose norm is 1. Any vector can be converted into a unit vector by dividing it by its norm, $\hat{\mathbf{u}} = \frac{\mathbf{u}}{\|\mathbf{u}\|}$. This process is called **normalization** of a vector.

Definition 23. A set of vectors $\{\mathbf{u}_i \in V \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ in an inner product space are **mutually orthonormal** or form an **orthonormal set** if their inner product $\langle \mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{u}_j \rangle = \delta_i^j$.

Theorem 6. *The standard basis vectors $\{\mathbf{e}_i\}$ form an orthonormal set for the Hilbert space F^n .*

Definition 24. The **component** of a vector \mathbf{u} along another vector \mathbf{v} is given by,

$$\text{comp}_{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{\langle \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u} \rangle}{\|\mathbf{v}\|} \quad (2.6)$$

The component measures what portion of one vector lies along another vector.

Definition 25. The **projection** of a vector \mathbf{u} along another vector \mathbf{v} is given by,

$$\text{proj}_{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{u}_{\parallel \mathbf{v}} = \langle \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u} \rangle \frac{\mathbf{v}}{\|\mathbf{v}\|^2} = \text{comp}_{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{u}) \frac{\mathbf{v}}{\|\mathbf{v}\|} \quad (2.7)$$

If a vector \mathbf{u} is split into two vectors, $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_{\parallel \mathbf{v}} + \mathbf{u}_{\perp \mathbf{v}}$, such that one of them is parallel to another vector \mathbf{v} ($\mathbf{u}_{\parallel \mathbf{v}}$) while the other is perpendicular ($\mathbf{u}_{\perp \mathbf{v}}$), then the vector $\mathbf{u}_{\parallel \mathbf{v}}$ that minimizes the length of the other is the projection \mathbf{u} along \mathbf{v} .

It is also worth mentioning that the component of a vector $\mathbf{a} \in F^n$ along the i th standard basis vector \mathbf{e}_i , $\langle \mathbf{e}_i, \mathbf{a} \rangle = a_i$.

Definition 26. The **Gram-Schmidt process** is an algorithm for producing a set of orthonormal vectors from a set of linearly independent vectors, $\{\mathbf{u}_i \mid i = 1, \dots, n\}$, where $n \leq \dim(V)$. The steps are as follows,

1. Choose the first vector from the set and normalize it, $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_1 = \frac{\mathbf{u}_1}{\|\mathbf{u}_1\|}$, set $i = 2$
2. For each vector \mathbf{u}_i , calculate $\mathbf{u}'_i = \mathbf{u}_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \langle \hat{\mathbf{u}}_j, \mathbf{u}_i \rangle \hat{\mathbf{u}}_j = \mathbf{u}_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \text{proj}_{\hat{\mathbf{u}}_j}(\mathbf{u}_i)$
3. Set $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_i = \frac{\mathbf{u}'_i}{\|\mathbf{u}'_i\|}$
4. Increase i by 1 and repeat from step 2 until $i = n$

The final set $\{\hat{\mathbf{u}}_i \mid i = 1, \dots, n\}$ is a set of mutually orthonormal vectors.

2.1.4 Linear Transformations and Matrices

Definition 27. A **linear transformation** is a mapping between two vector spaces U and V over the field F , $T : U \mapsto V$, such that, $\forall \mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_2 \in U$ and $a_1, a_2 \in F$,

$$T(a_1 \mathbf{u}_1 + a_2 \mathbf{u}_2) = a_1 T(\mathbf{u}_1) + a_2 T(\mathbf{u}_2) \in V \quad (2.8)$$

For a review of matrices and their operations: addition, subtraction, multiplication, inversion, transposition, Hermitian conjugation, the reader is referred to [45].

Theorem 7. Any linear transformation $T : F^m \mapsto F^n$ can be represented by an $n \times m$ matrix $\mathcal{M}_T \in F_{n \times m}$ such that,

$$\mathbf{v}_{n \times 1} = T(\mathbf{u}) = \mathcal{M}_T \mathbf{u}_{m \times 1} \in F^n, \forall \mathbf{u} \in F^m \quad (2.9)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_{m \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{v}_{n \times 1}$ are the column vector representations of the vectors $\mathbf{u} \in F^m$ and $\mathbf{v} \in F^n$ respectively.

The next theorem provides a way to compute the entries of the matrix \mathcal{M}_T corresponding to a linear transformation T .

Theorem 8. If \mathcal{M}_T is the matrix corresponding to a linear transformation $T : F^m \mapsto F^n$, then its i th column consists of the components of $T(\mathbf{e}_i)$ with respect to a choice of bases $\{\mathbf{e}'_j \mid j = 1, \dots, n\}$ for F^n , where $\{\mathbf{e}_i \mid i = 1, \dots, m\}$ is the basis for F^m .

In an inner product space, the matrix \mathcal{M}_T can be written succinctly as,

$$\mathcal{M}_T = \begin{bmatrix} \langle \mathbf{e}'_1, T(\mathbf{e}_1) \rangle & \langle \mathbf{e}'_1, T(\mathbf{e}_2) \rangle & \dots & \langle \mathbf{e}'_1, T(\mathbf{e}_m) \rangle \\ \langle \mathbf{e}'_2, T(\mathbf{e}_1) \rangle & \cdot & \dots & \langle \mathbf{e}'_2, T(\mathbf{e}_m) \rangle \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ \langle \mathbf{e}'_n, T(\mathbf{e}_1) \rangle & \langle \mathbf{e}'_n, T(\mathbf{e}_2) \rangle & \dots & \langle \mathbf{e}'_n, T(\mathbf{e}_m) \rangle \end{bmatrix}_{n \times m}, \quad \mathcal{M}_{T_{i,j}} = \langle \mathbf{e}'_i, T(\mathbf{e}_j) \rangle \quad (2.10)$$

Definition 28. A **linear operator** on a vector space V is a linear transformation that maps from the space to itself, $T : V \mapsto V$.

Theorem 9. An operator $T : F^n \mapsto F^n$ can be represented by an $n \times n$ square matrix.

It is necessary to classify various types of matrices required for our study.

Definition 29. A **Diagonal matrix** is a square matrix having zeros everywhere except the principle diagonal.

Definition 30. A **Symmetric matrix** is a square matrix A whose transpose is equal to itself, that is, $A^T = A$.

Definition 31. A **Skew-symmetric matrix** is a square matrix A whose transpose is equal to the negative of itself, that is, $A^T = -A$.

Definition 32. A **Hermitian (or self-adjoint) matrix** is a square matrix A which is equal to its Hermitian conjugate, that is, $A = A^\dagger$.

Definition 33. A **Skew-hermitian matrix** is a square matrix A which is equal to the negative of its Hermitian conjugate, that is, $A = -A^\dagger$.

Definition 34. An **Involutory or self-inverse matrix** is a square matrix A which is its own inverse, that is, $A = A^{-1}$.

Definition 35. A **Unitary matrix** is a square matrix A whose hermitian conjugate is equal to its inverse, that is, $A^\dagger = A^{-1}$.

2.1.5 Eigenvalues, eigenvectors and change of basis

Given a linear operator $T : V \mapsto V$ on a vector space V over a field F , there may exist some vectors whose outputs under the transformation are proportional to themselves. These vectors and their proportionality constants are significant in understanding the operator.

Definition 36. For a linear operator $T : V \mapsto V$ on a vector space V over a field F , the vectors $\mathbf{v} \in V$ for which,

$$T(\mathbf{v}) = \lambda \mathbf{v}, \lambda \in F \quad (2.11)$$

are called the eigenvectors of the operator T and the scalar λ is the corresponding eigenvalue of \mathbf{v} .

Lemma 1. A scalar multiple of an eigenvector of an operator is also an eigenvector of that operator with the same eigenvalue.

It might happen that multiple linearly independent eigenvectors correspond to the same eigenvalue. Then the eigenvalue is said to be **degenerate** having multiplicity equal to the number of linearly independent eigenvectors it corresponds to.

Lemma 2. A linear combination of the eigenvectors (sometimes referred to as degenerate eigenvectors) corresponding to the same degenerate eigenvalue is also an eigenvector having the same eigenvalue.

Definition 37. If the eigenvectors of a linear operator form a basis for the vector space, then the basis formed by the eigenvectors is called an **eigenbasis**.

The components of a vector written in column vector representation depends on the choice of basis. When we have different choices of basis for the same vector space, it becomes necessary to convert between these bases. Luckily, such a conversion considers linear combinations of the old basis vectors as new basis vectors and so, can be defined using a linear transformation.

Definition 38. A **change of basis transformation** is a linear transformation that converts a vector from one choice of bases to another.

Theorem 10. *The matrix corresponding to the change of basis transformation is the consists of the column vector representation of the old basis vectors in the new bases as columns.*

If $\{e_i\}$ and $\{e'_i\}$ are sets of the old and the new basis vectors and $e_j = \sum_{i=1}^n p_{ij}e'_i$, then the change of basis transformation matrix is $\mathcal{P} = [p_{ij}]_{n \times n}$. Therefore, any column vector represented in the old basis \mathbf{u} transforms into the vector $\mathbf{u}' = \mathcal{P}\mathbf{u}$ in the new basis.

Theorem 11. *The change of basis transformation matrix between two orthonormal bases is unitary.*

Upon a change of basis, the matrices corresponding to the linear operators defined on the vector space change its components, given that they were originally defined using the basis vectors as in Theorem 8.

Theorem 12. *Upon change of basis of a vector space using a basis transformation matrix \mathcal{P} , the matrix corresponding to a linear operator T in the old basis, \mathcal{M}_T , changes to $\mathcal{M}'_T = \mathcal{P}\mathcal{M}_T\mathcal{P}^{-1}$ in the new basis.*

The matrices \mathcal{M}_T and \mathcal{M}'_T are called **similar matrices**.

Theorem 13. *Basis transformation between orthonormal bases preserves the trace and determinant of similar matrices.*

If the eigenvectors of an operator on a vector space form an eigenbasis of that vector space, then there is also a basis transformation matrix corresponding to this.

Definition 39. A **similarity transformation matrix** is the change of basis linear transformation matrix corresponding to conversion to an eigenbasis of an operator.

Theorem 14. *The similarity transformation matrix for an operator is the inverse of the matrix consisting of the components of its linearly independent eigenvectors in the original basis as columns.*

Definition 40. A **similarity transformation** is the transformation of the matrix corresponding to a linear operator on a vector space under basis transformation to the eigenbasis of that linear operator.

The resulting matrix corresponding to the linear operator is usually diagonal, and so this process is also known as **diagonalization** of a matrix. Diagonal matrices are easier to work with, so it would be helpful to know when a matrix is diagonalizable.

Theorem 15. *A matrix is diagonalizable if and only if its eigenvectors span the space, that is, form an eigenbasis.*

At this point we define the commutator of two square matrices⁷.

⁷The commutator can be defined for operators on vector spaces of any dimension in general, but we will not require such generality

Definition 41. The **commutator** of two square matrices S and T is given by,

$$[S, T] = ST - TS \quad (2.12)$$

Definition 42. A **normal matrix** N is a matrix satisfying the following relation,

$$[N^\dagger, N] = [N, N^\dagger] = \mathbf{0} \quad (2.13)$$

where $\mathbf{0}$ is the null matrix.

In other words, a matrix is normal if it commutes with its hermitian conjugate.

Theorem 16. *Normal matrices have eigenvectors that form an eigenbasis and thus, are diagonalizable.*

Given two diagonalizable matrices, it is sometimes possible to diagonalize them using the same similarity transformation matrix. Such two matrices are called **simultaneously diagonalizable**.

Theorem 17. *Two matrices \mathcal{M}_T and \mathcal{M}_S are simultaneously diagonalizable if and only if they commute, that is,*

$$[\mathcal{M}_T, \mathcal{M}_S] = \mathbf{0} \quad (2.14)$$

2.1.6 Properties of Hermitian and Unitary Operators

Every square matrix can be thought of as a linear operator on the vector space. Thus Hermitian and Unitary matrices also correspond to linear operators.

A linear operator whose corresponding matrix is Hermitian is called a **Hermitian or self-adjoint linear operator**⁸. The following theorem provides some important properties of Hermitian linear operators.

Theorem 18. *For a Hermitian linear operator on a complex finite-dimensional vector space,*

- *The eigenvalues are real*
- *The eigenvectors are mutually orthogonal*
- *The eigenvectors form an orthogonal basis of the vector space*⁹

Lemma 3. The determinant of a Hermitian matrix is real.

⁸There is a subtle difference between these two. In fact, we are working with self-adjoint operators, but for our studies, we will not make any distinction between the two

⁹This result does not extend in general to infinite dimensions, yet in quantum mechanics, we assume this to be true. For quantum computing, since the spaces are finite-dimensional, the theorem holds true

Thus for Hermitian operators on finite-dimensional complex vector spaces, it is guaranteed that their eigenvectors form an orthonormal basis of the vector space (they can be normalized to make them orthonormal). Even if some of the eigenvalues are degenerate, Gram-Schmidt orthonormalization and lemma 2 allows for them to be converted into an orthonormal set of vectors. It follows from Theorem 18 that Hermitian operators have eigenvectors that always form an eigenbasis of the vector space, so they can always be diagonalized. Moreover, it has another important property.

Theorem 19. *The similarity transformation matrix corresponding to a Hermitian operator is always unitary.*

The diagonalizability of Hermitian along with Unitary matrices also follow from their normality by Theorem 17.

Theorem 19 is the consequence of Theorem 14 and the theorem stated below.

Theorem 20. *The columns of a unitary matrix consist of mutually orthonormal vectors.*

Some more properties on unitary matrices are as follows,

Lemma 4. Unitary matrices have unit determinant.

Theorem 21. *Unitary operators preserve inner products, hence norm and metric induced by the inner product in inner product spaces.*

It is beneficial to introduce the bra-ket notation of quantum mechanics, used throughout quantum computing and error correction, at this juncture to aid in further explanation regarding the effect of operators on inner products in Hilbert spaces.

2.1.7 Dual Spaces, Bra-ket Notation and the Projection Operator

From now on, we will write vectors $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in V$ as $|u\rangle, |v\rangle$, the symbol $|\cdot\rangle$ is called a **ket**. A linear operator O acting on a vector $|u\rangle$ can be written as $O|u\rangle = |Ou\rangle$.

Definition 43. A **dual vector space** of a vector space V over the field F , denoted by V^* , is the set of linear maps between V and F . Each element of the dual vector space is called a **dual vector**.

An inner product takes two vectors and returns a scalar. Therefore, corresponding to each vector $|u\rangle$ in a vector field V , we can assign a **dual vector** denoted by $\langle u|$ such that acting on any vector $|v\rangle \in V$ it produces a scalar, $\langle u|v\rangle \in F$ such that $\langle u|v\rangle = \langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle$. When $|u\rangle$ is written in column vector representation in any basis, then its corresponding dual vector $\langle u|$ is its hermitian

conjugate row vector, $\langle u | = \mathbf{u}^\dagger$. Similarly, the dual vector corresponding to $|Ou\rangle$, where O is a linear operator in its matrix form¹⁰, is, $\langle Ou | = \langle u | O^\dagger$. Putting it all together,

$$\langle O_1 u | O_2 v \rangle = \langle u | O_1^\dagger O_2 | v \rangle \quad (2.15)$$

where O_1, O_2 are two linear operators in matrix representation.

This is the **bra-ket notation**¹¹ of quantum mechanics (and quantum computing).

Hermitian operators give the same inner product when acted on either the vector or its dual.

$$\langle u | H v \rangle = \langle u | H | v \rangle = \langle u | H^\dagger | v \rangle = \langle H u | v \rangle \quad (2.16)$$

where H is a Hermitian operator.

Unitary operators, on the other hand, preserve inner products, along with the norms and metrics induced by it.

$$\langle U u | U v \rangle = \langle u | U^\dagger U | v \rangle = \langle u | U^{-1} U | v \rangle = \langle u | v \rangle \quad (2.17)$$

where U is a Unitary operator. They correspond to "rotations" of the vectors without changing their lengths or angles between them¹².

The projection of the vector $|v\rangle$ on the unit vector $|u\rangle$ can be written as $\langle u | v \rangle |u\rangle$. More generally, a **projection operator** or **projector** for a unit vector $|u\rangle$ is defined as,

$$P_u = Proj_u = |u\rangle \langle u| = \sum_i u_i |e_i\rangle \langle e_i| \quad (2.18)$$

where $\{|e_i\rangle\}$ is an orthonormal basis and $\{u_i\}$ are the components of $|u\rangle$ in that basis. The projection operator P in a Hilbert space has the following properties,

- **Idempotency:** $P^2 = P$
- **Linearity:** For any scalars a, b and vectors $|u\rangle, |v\rangle$: $P(a|u\rangle + b|v\rangle) = aP|u\rangle + bP|v\rangle$
- **Hermitian Property (for Orthogonal Projections):** $P^\dagger = P$

To find the projection of any vector $|v\rangle$ along $|u\rangle$, we simply let the projector of $|u\rangle$ act on $|v\rangle$, that is,

$$proj_u \mathbf{v} = Proj_u |v\rangle = |u\rangle \langle u | v \rangle \quad (2.19)$$

¹⁰Here the following theorem on hermitian conjugate of the product of matrices is useful: $(AB)^\dagger = B^\dagger A^\dagger$

¹¹The bra-ket notation was introduced by Paul Adrian Maurice Dirac, a Nobel laureate physicist with outstanding contributions to quantum mechanics

¹²This will be better understood using the Bloch sphere as discussed in subsection 2.2.2

2.1.8 Tensor product of matrices and vectors

The **tensor product** between two matrices¹³ $A = [a_{ij}]_{r_1 \times c_1}$ and $B = [b_{ij}]_{r_2 \times c_2}$ is given by,

$$A \otimes B = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11}B & a_{12}B & \cdot & \cdot & a_{1c_1-1}B & a_{1c_1}B \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ a_{r_1 1}B & a_{r_1 2}B & \cdot & \cdot & a_{r_1 c_1-1}B & a_{r_1 c_1}B \end{bmatrix}_{r_1 r_2 \times c_1 c_2} \quad (2.20)$$

where,

$$a_{ij}B = \begin{bmatrix} a_{ij}b_{11} & a_{ij}b_{12} & \cdot & \cdot & a_{ij}b_{1c_2-1} & a_{ij}b_{1c_2} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ a_{ij}b_{r_2 1} & a_{ij}b_{r_2 2} & \cdot & \cdot & a_{ij}b_{r_2 c_2-1} & a_{ij}b_{r_2 c_2} \end{bmatrix}_{r_2 \times c_2} \quad (2.21)$$

The tensor product of vectors can be calculated in the same way, it being a special case where $c_1 = c_2 = 1$. But for vectors, the tensor product symbol \otimes is usually dropped,

$$|u\rangle \otimes |v\rangle = |u\rangle |v\rangle = |uv\rangle$$

It should be noted that the tensor product is not commutative.

2.2 Background for Quantum Computation and Quantum Error Correction

2.2.1 Quantum States, Observables, Measurement, Dynamics and Assembly

A quantum system in quantum computing has 4 key components, taken as postulates, as follows:

1. **State:** The current state of the system is represented by a unit vector in a Hilbert space
2. **Observables:** The quantities that can be observed are represented by Hermitian operators
3. **Measurement:** Measurement of any observable returns any one of the eigenvalues of the

¹³The tensor product is usually defined more generally between tensors of any rank, and this is a special case considering vectors and matrices as rank 1 and rank 2 tensors. But for our purposes, such generality is not required

corresponding Hermitian operator as the measured value of the observable and the state vector of the system collapses to the corresponding eigenvector

4. **Dynamics:** Between two measurements, the time evolution of the system can be represented as Unitary operators

In a nutshell, this is what constitutes all quantum computing [40].

Quantum States

The quantum state of a system is represented by a vector in a Hilbert space over the field of complex numbers. The choice of the Hilbert space depends on the quantum system in consideration. A quantum state remains as a normalized superposition of all possible observable states for some observable (given by a Hermitian operator) until it is observed. When expanded in any basis of the space (usually the eigenbasis of the Hermitian operator corresponding to the observable), a quantum state

$$|u\rangle = \sum_i u_i |e_i\rangle \quad (2.22)$$

has probability $\frac{|u_i|^2}{\sum_j |u_j|^2}$ of being in state $|e_i\rangle$ when measured, according to the Born rule [43] [46].

The u_i 's are called the complex **probability amplitudes** of the corresponding state. Due to the probabilistic interpretation of the components, the vectors are usually normalized and so the probability of being in state $|e_i\rangle$ is $|u_i|^2$. We assume all vectors corresponding to quantum states to be normalized.

The probability of a quantum state $|v\rangle$ to be found in state $|u\rangle$ upon measurement is given by their inner product as $|\langle u | v \rangle|^2 = \langle u | v \rangle \langle u | v \rangle^*$. The dimension of the state vector represents the number of possible states in which the system can be found in after measurement. It can be infinite, but for Quantum Computing this is finite.

Observables

Corresponding to every observable of a quantum system is a Hermitian operator. The operator can be written as a square matrix, in our finite-dimensional setting. By Theorem 18 and lemma 1, such an operator has a set of orthonormal eigenvectors that span the vector space. Each of these eigenvectors corresponds to a possible state of the quantum system after measurement and the corresponding eigenvalue is the possible value of the observable. The eigenvectors are usually referred to as eigenstates of the system [43]. Theorem 18 also ensures that the observed quantity is real. The orthogonality ensures that any two states are mutually exclusive. Without measuring the observable, we can still calculate the average value of the observable,

more precisely, the expectation value of the observable corresponding to a Hermitian operator¹⁴ H ¹⁵ of a quantum state $|u\rangle$ in the following way:

$$\langle H \rangle = E(H) = \langle u | H | u \rangle = \langle u | H u \rangle = \sum_i u_i^* u_i \langle e_i | H e_i \rangle = \sum_i \lambda_i |u_i|^2 \quad (2.23)$$

where $\{e_i\}$ is an eigenbasis of the operator H and $\{\lambda_i\}$ the corresponding eigenvalues.

Measurement

Measurement of an observable on a quantum system is a process whose dynamics is not wholly known. However, what is known is that after measurement, the observable takes a value equal to one of the eigenvalues of the Hermitian operator corresponding to the measurement. The state of the system instantly collapses to the unit eigenvector (lemma 1) corresponding to the observed eigenvalue. This can be summarized as,

Before measurement

$$|u\rangle = \sum_i u_i |e_i\rangle \quad (2.24)$$

where e_i is an eigenvector of the Hermitian operator H with eigenvalue λ_i

After measurement

$$|u\rangle = |e_i\rangle, \text{ with probability } |u_i|^2 \quad (2.25)$$

with the observed value of the observable being λ_i with the same probability. It is to be noted that after the state collapses to any one of the eigenstates by observing it, each corresponding observation will return the same state given that no time passes between the two observations.

Dynamics

The dynamics¹⁶ of the quantum system is given by a unitary operator. If a system is in state u_t initially at time t , then at time $t + 1$, its state is given by,

$$|u_{t+1}\rangle = U(t) |u_t\rangle \quad (2.26)$$

¹⁴It is a convention in quantum mechanics to denote the value of the operator as H and the operator as \hat{H} [42]. But we will not use such convention here

¹⁵Although H or \hat{H} is reserved for the Hamiltonian in quantum mechanics, we will use this to mean a Hermitian operator throughout as no mention of the Hamiltonian occurs

¹⁶In general the dynamics is given by the Schrodinger equation [47], which can be reduced to unitary operators in finite-dimensional space

and the states at time $t + 2$, $t + 3$ and so on are given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 |u_{t+2}\rangle &= U(t + 1) |u_{t+1}\rangle = U(t) |u_t\rangle \\
 |u_{t+3}\rangle &= U(t + 2) |u_{t+2}\rangle = U(t + 2)U(t + 1) |u_{t+1}\rangle = U(t + 2)U(t + 1)U(t) |u_t\rangle \\
 &\dots \quad (2.27) \\
 |u_{t+n}\rangle &= \left[\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} U(t + i) \right] |u_t\rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

[17] where we assume the process to be divided into discrete time steps, as is usually the case in computing.

The operator needs to be unitary as unitary operators preserve norms (theorem 21), leaving normalized vectors as normalized so that the probability interpretation of the components is not violated upon time evolution, as is also ensured by the Schrodinger equation [42].

Time reversal corresponds to multiplying the bra vector corresponding to a ket vector to the left¹⁷ of the unitary operator matrix,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle u_{t-1}| &= \langle u_t| U(t) \\
 \text{or, } |u_{t-1}\rangle &= U^\dagger(t) |u_t\rangle = U^{-1}(t) |u_t\rangle
 \end{aligned} \quad (2.28)$$

providing another reason for the dynamics to be governed by unitary operators.

Assembling quantum systems

When two independent quantum systems represented by Hilbert spaces \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 form a single quantum system, then the combined state vector space of the system \mathcal{H} is given by their tensor product,

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2 \quad (2.29)$$

If the first system is in state $|u_1\rangle$ and the second is in state $|u_2\rangle$, then the whole system is in state $|u_1 \otimes u_2\rangle = |u_1 u_2\rangle$.

2.2.2 Qubits and Quantum Gates

The fundamental unit of information in classical systems is **bit**. Plainly speaking, a bit represents the amount of information that allows one to choose between two equally probable possibilities. These mutually exclusive, hence orthogonal, choices can be labelled $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$

¹⁷The reason for this is fully explored in chapter 3 in [40]

and represented as,

$$|0\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, |1\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.30)$$

Quantum bits, or qubits in short, are a superposition of these two mutually orthogonal classical states.

Qubits

A **qubit** is a unit of information that describes a two-dimensional quantum system. A qubit can be represented as a unit vector in a two-dimensional Hilbert space, the ℓ_2 space over the field of complex number. Mathematically, a qubit $|q\rangle$ can be written as,

$$|q\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} = \alpha \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \beta \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle \quad (2.31)$$

where $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ and $\alpha^2 + \beta^2 = 1$. In short, qubits are unit vectors in the Hilbert space \mathbb{C}^2 . The set of classical bits $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$ forms a basis for this vector space.

Practically, any physical two-state quantum system can be used to create qubits. For example, an electron in an atom with two energy states, a photon with two polarizations, a sub-atomic particle that can be in two directions, electron spin, etc. A system with 2^n possible states can be represented as a combination of n qubits.

Multiple qubit systems can be created by combining them using tensor products. An n -qubit system corresponds to a Hilbert space represented by,

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathbb{C}^2 \otimes \dots \otimes \mathbb{C}^2, (n \text{ times}) = (\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n} \quad (2.32)$$

which is equivalent¹⁸ to the \mathbb{C}^{2^n} ℓ_2 space having dimension 2^n . The basis vectors for this set are all possible combinations of n $|0\rangle$'s and $|1\rangle$'s, $\{|0\dots 0\rangle, \dots, |1\dots 1\rangle\}$. In particular, a two-qubit system can be written as,

$$|q_1 q_2\rangle = c_{0,0} |0_A 0_B\rangle + c_{0,1} |0_A 1_B\rangle + c_{1,0} |1_A 0_B\rangle + c_{1,1} |1_A 1_B\rangle \quad (2.33)$$

where the subscripts mean they are from parallel branches, and,

$$|00\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, |01\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, |10\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, |11\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.34)$$

¹⁸The proper mathematical term is **isomorphic**, but the details are unnecessary for our purposes

The set of all possible unit vectors in \mathbb{C}^{2^2} is larger than the set of all states that can occur as the combined state vector of two qubits as tensor product. In general, there are some possible quantum states representing n qubit systems that cannot be written as a tensor product of n separate qubits. These are called **entangled states**. Four such states in a two-qubit system are,

$$|\Phi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0_A0_B\rangle + |1_A1_B\rangle) \quad (2.35a)$$

$$|\Phi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0_A0_B\rangle - |1_A1_B\rangle) \quad (2.35b)$$

$$|\Psi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0_A1_B\rangle + |1_A0_B\rangle) \quad (2.35c)$$

$$|\Psi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0_A1_B\rangle - |1_A0_B\rangle) \quad (2.35d)$$

These are called **Bell states** or **EPR pairs**¹⁹ [10]. These states form a basis for the two-qubit state Hilbert space. They are said to be equally or maximally entangled as in each of them both eigenstates are equally probable with probabilities $(\pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}})^2 = \frac{1}{2}$ each.

Figure 2.2: Bloch sphere

In quantum computing and quantum communication, it does not matter if the whole qubit is multiplied by an arbitrary phase factor $e^{i\gamma}$. As such, a qubit can be written as follows,

$$|q\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle \equiv \cos\theta |0\rangle + e^{i\phi} \sin\theta |1\rangle \quad (2.36)$$

¹⁹More specifically, they are called the four maximally entangled Bell states

where the ϕ is called the phase of the qubit and θ depends on the probability of each of $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. This can also be represented on a sphere called a **Bloch sphere** as shown in Figure 2.2²⁰. On a Bloch sphere, the probability angle θ corresponds to the latitude and the phase ϕ corresponds to the longitude as shown in the figure. Unitary operators correspond to rotations on the Bloch sphere.

Quantum Gates

Classical logic gates take one or more digital logical inputs and return a digital logical output. Digital inputs are bits 0 or 1 represented by 0 and ± 5 volts practically. AND, OR, NOT, NAND, NOR, XOR and XNOR are well-known examples of such gates [48]. They are physically implemented using semiconductor devices like transistors, MOSFETs etc. In short, classical gates act on classical bits to return a classical bit. Quantum gates are their quantum analogue.

Quantum logical gates or **quantum gates** act on qubits to return output qubits. Similar to classical logic gates, quantum gates are the building block of quantum circuits. However, quantum gates are different from their classical analogues in two ways:

1. They preserve superposition of states and the norm of the qubit
2. They are reversible

As stated above, the dynamics of a quantum system is governed by unitary operators. So, quantum gates can be represented by unitary matrices²¹. This also restricts any quantum gate to have as many outputs as inputs, since unitary matrices are square matrices²². Erasing a qubit will cost energy as according to Landauer's principle [40], information erasure costs energy, making it better to not destroy any input qubits. A qubit $|\Phi\rangle$ passing through a quantum gate A can be written as,

$$A|\Phi\rangle = |A\Phi\rangle \quad (2.37)$$

A **circuit** is a combination of sequential and parallel operations represented by gates/matrices. A **quantum circuit** is a circuit with quantum gates. Before proceeding further, we need to discuss how sequential (or series) and parallel combination of gates in a circuit are represented using matrices.

Assume that a qubit passes through two quantum gates A and B sequentially.

$$|\Phi\rangle \longrightarrow \boxed{A} \longrightarrow \boxed{B} \longrightarrow |\Phi'\rangle$$

²⁰The figure is taken from [40]

²¹Classical gates also have matrix representation when bits are represented as column vectors

²²On the contrary, a classical gate with m input bits and n output bits will have size $2^n \times 2^m$

Then, $|\Phi'\rangle = BA|\Phi\rangle = |BA\Phi\rangle$. It is to be noted that A acts on $|\Phi\rangle$ before B . B acts on $|A\Phi\rangle$. Here BA is simply the matrix multiplication between A and B .

Similarly, if two qubits $|\Phi_A\rangle$ and $|\Phi_B\rangle$ ²³ move through two gates A and B respectively in parallel,

then, the combined initial two-qubit state can be written as,

$$\begin{aligned} |\Phi_A\rangle \otimes |\Phi_B\rangle &= |\Phi_A\Phi_B\rangle \\ \text{where, } |\Phi'_A\rangle &= |A\Phi_A\rangle \\ |\Phi'_B\rangle &= |B\Phi_B\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (2.38)$$

and the combined final two-qubit state can be written as,

$$|\Phi'_A\Phi'_B\rangle = |\Phi'_A\rangle \otimes |\Phi'_B\rangle = |A\Phi_A\rangle \otimes |B\Phi_B\rangle = (A \otimes B) |\Phi_A\Phi_B\rangle \quad (2.39)$$

Thus, both the parallel combination of qubits and the gates acting on the parallel branches can be written using the tensor product.

As stated before, quantum gates need to be unitary. A quantum gate can be unary (takes a single qubit as input), binary (takes two qubits as input), ternary (takes three input qubits) or m-ary (taking m qubits as input). In all cases, the number of output equals the number of inputs. A list of well-known quantum gates are produced below:

1. **Identity Gate:** This gate returns the input qubit without any change.

$$I = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.40)$$

is a unary identity gate.

2. **Pauli Gates:** Unary gates denoted by X, Y, Z or $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$ and defined as follows:

$$X = \sigma_x = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, Y = \sigma_y = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{bmatrix}, Z = \sigma_z = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.41)$$

The X gate is actually a bit flip or NOT gate and Z is a phase flip and are used to represent bit flip and phase flip channels respectively. These matrices are involutory.

²³The subscripts are used to denote qubits on different branches of a circuit

3. **Square-root of NOT gate:** It is a unary gate defined by

$$\sqrt{NOT} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \sqrt{NOT} \cdot \sqrt{NOT} = X \quad (2.42)$$

4. **Hadamard gate:** The unary Hadamard gate is defined as,

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.43)$$

5. **Phase shift gates:** The general phase shift gate is a unary gate defined as,

$$P(\varphi) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\varphi} \end{bmatrix}, P^\dagger(\varphi) = P(-\varphi) \quad (2.44)$$

and the Z, S, T gates are special cases of $P(\varphi)$,

$$Z = P(\pi) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, S = P\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i \end{bmatrix}, T = P\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\frac{\pi}{4}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.45)$$

6. **Rotation operators:** The rotation operators $R_x(\theta)$, $R_y(\theta)$, $R_z(\theta)$ are defined as follows:

$$R_x(\theta) = e^{-iX\theta/2} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta/2) & -i \sin(\theta/2) \\ -i \sin(\theta/2) & \cos(\theta/2) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.46a)$$

$$R_y(\theta) = e^{-iY\theta/2} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta/2) & -\sin(\theta/2) \\ \sin(\theta/2) & \cos(\theta/2) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.46b)$$

$$R_z(\theta) = e^{-iZ\theta/2} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-i\theta/2} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\theta/2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.46c)$$

corresponding to x, y, z -axes rotations by θ respectively.

7. **Controlled U gates:** In quantum computing, the binary gates usually have a control qubit depending on which an operation U is done on the second qubit, making it a controlled U gate. This can be written as,

$$CU = \langle 0_1 | I_1 I_2 + \langle 1_1 | I_1 U_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & u_{00} & u_{01} \\ 0 & 0 & u_{10} & u_{11} \end{bmatrix}, U = \begin{bmatrix} u_{00} & u_{01} \\ u_{10} & u_{11} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.47)$$

where the subscript 1 means that it acts on the first qubit and subscript 2 means that it

acts on the second qubit. Different subscripts mean that the operations are on parallel branches, so the operation on one subscript cannot act on the other. The equation above concisely states the following: an operation U is done on the second qubit when the first qubit (the control qubit) is $|1\rangle$ and leaves the second qubit unchanged if the first is $|0\rangle$. In both cases, the first qubit is usually left unchanged. Controlled versions of X, Y, Z gates are called CX, CY, CZ respectively where $U = X, Y, \text{ or } Z$ respectively. CX is also called $CNOT$ gate.

$$CNOT = CX = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, CNOT |x, y\rangle = |x, x \oplus y\rangle \quad (2.48a)$$

$$CZ = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, CZ \begin{cases} |11\rangle = -|11\rangle, \\ |x, y\rangle = |x, y\rangle, \text{ otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.48b)$$

Here, \oplus denotes the classical XOR operation. The CNOT and CZ gates bit flip and phase flip the second qubit respectively if the control qubit is $|1\rangle$. The following are the circuit representations of these gates.

8. **Toffoli Gate:** A Toffoli gate or CCNOT gate is a ternary gate with two control qubits. It is like a CNOT with two control qubits, bit flipping the third qubit only when the first two are in state $|11\rangle$.

$$Toff = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, Toff |x, y, z\rangle = |x, y, z \oplus (x \wedge y)\rangle \quad (2.49)$$

where \wedge denotes the logical AND operation from classical logic.

9. **Fredkin gate:** The Fredkin gate or CSWAP gate is another ternary gate having one con-

trol qubit. It swaps the second and third qubits if the first one is $|1\rangle$.

$$CSWAP = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, CSWAP \begin{cases} |0, y, z\rangle = |0, y, z\rangle, \\ |1, y, z\rangle = |1, z, y\rangle \end{cases} \quad (2.50)$$

Their circuit diagrams are given below

2.2.3 Pure and Mixed States, Density operator and the Krauss operator

A system consisting of a qubit or a number of parallel qubits remaining in a quantum superposition of all of its basis states (some components might be zero) is said to be in a **pure state**. When measurements are done on any one of the (or multiple) qubits in an ensemble of similar systems, the measurements will give the possible states with some probability equal to the modulus squared of their probability amplitudes. This is called the reduction of a qubit to a probabilistic bit or pbit [5]. But the measurement can be done on some of the qubits, leaving the others in a superposition. More precisely, suppose that a multiple qubit system in a state of superposition can be factorized into the following tensor product.

$$|\psi\rangle_{system} = \alpha |0_A\rangle \left(\sum_i a_i |\psi_i\rangle_{remaining} \right) + \beta |1_A\rangle \left(\sum_i b_i |\psi_i\rangle_{remaining} \right) \quad (2.51)$$

then performing a measurement of the qubit of subsystem A will reduce the whole system to a probabilistic system where two possible superpositions exist.

$$|\psi\rangle_{system} \xrightarrow{\text{measurement}_A} \begin{cases} |0_A\rangle \sum_i a_i |\psi_i\rangle_{remaining} : \text{probability } |\alpha|^2 \\ |1_A\rangle \sum_i b_i |\psi_i\rangle_{remaining} : \text{probability } |\beta|^2 \end{cases} \quad (2.52)$$

This situation where the system is in a state of two or more possible quantum superpositions probabilistically is called a **mixed state**. In simpler terms, mixed states are the result of measuring some but not all the qubits of the system, rendering it into a combination of classical

probabilistic and quantum superpositioned states.

The density operator formulation of Quantum Computing (and Quantum Mechanics in general) is equivalent to the formulation with quantum states. The **density operator** or **density matrix** of a quantum state vector $|\Phi\rangle$ is given by,

$$\rho = \sum_i p_i |\psi_i\rangle \langle\psi_i| \quad (2.53)$$

where p_i is the probability of the state $|\psi_i\rangle$ ²⁴. The density operator reduces to the projection operator for pure states, since they have probability 1 of being in that state. The states themselves might be a superposition of $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ and are not to be confused with these basic states themselves. The density operator is hermitian, idempotent and does not have any global phase ambiguity. A comparison can be made between the state vector and density operator formulation as shown in Table 2.1:

Table 2.1: Comparison between state vector and density operator formalism

	State vector	Density operator
Normalization:	$\langle\psi \psi\rangle = 1$	$Tr(\rho) = 1$
Transition probability:	$ \langle\phi \psi\rangle ^2$	$\langle\phi \rho \phi\rangle$
Expectation value:	$\langle H \rangle = \langle u H u \rangle$	$\langle H \rangle = Tr(\rho H)$
Time Evolution:	$U u \rangle$	$U \rho U^\dagger$

In quantum computation, the environment introduces errors in the system by slightly modifying its phases and amplitudes. The environment is usually modeled as independent and depolarizing, that is, affecting each qubit independently, which is analogous to the classical bit flip [17]. Considering the environment-system coupled time evolution operator to be U^{ES} acting jointly on the initial environment-system state $|0_E \psi_S\rangle$, we can write,

$$\begin{aligned} U^{ES} |0_E \psi_S\rangle &= \mathbb{I}^E U^{ES} |0_E \psi_S\rangle \\ &= \left(\sum_e |e_E\rangle \langle e_E| \right) U^{ES} |0_E\rangle |\psi_S\rangle \\ &= \sum_e |e_E\rangle \langle e_E| U^{ES} |0_E\rangle |\psi_S\rangle \\ &= \sum_e |e_E\rangle A_e^S |\psi_S\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (2.54)$$

where $|e_E\rangle$ is an orthonormal basis for the environment and $A_e^S = \langle e_E | U^{ES} |0_E\rangle$. The environment evolution part has been removed using the inner product leaving an operator that acts only

²⁴Here the subscript is simply the summation index not for identifying separate branches. That will be done in capital letters

on the system. When written in terms of the density operator, this leads to the Krauss operator formulation [11] of the environment,

$$U^{ES} \rho U^{\dagger ES} = \sum_e A_e \rho A_e^\dagger \quad (2.55)$$

where the superscript S is dropped in A_e as it is understood that it acts on the system alone.

2.3 Quantum Information and Error Correction

Information is what allows us to determine the actual outcome from different possible outcomes. A **bit** of information halves the number of possible outcomes. Such a quantitative description of information was introduced by C. Shannon in [49]. For any system whose set of possible discrete outcomes is distributed according to some probability distribution, the Shannon Entropy, that is, the amount of information received on average from a single outcome/measurement of the system in bits is given by²⁵,

$$H(S) = - \sum_i p_i \log_2(p_i) \quad (2.56)$$

where p_i is the probability of the i th possible outcome.

Quantum Information is "the type of information obtained when the state space of deterministic information is extended with arbitrary superpositions of deterministic states. Formally, each deterministic state is identified with one of an orthonormal basis vector in a Hilbert space and superpositions are unit-length vectors that are expressible as complex linear sums of the chosen basis vectors. Ultimately, it is convenient to extend this state space again by permitting probability distributions over the quantum states. This is still called quantum information" [5]. Thus, qubits are the units of quantum information.

Like classical information, quantum information needs to be sent over some channel to ensure quantum communication. It was shown by P. Shor [15] that entangled Bell pairs could communicate information. But the channel induces errors, simplest being bit flip and phase flip, thus destroying the quantum information stored in the superposition. This leads to the concept of **Quantum Error Correction**. Quantum Repetition Codes are the simplest form of error correction. It simply means sending the same information multiple times. This along with entanglement provides scope for improvement in error correction as explored in [37]. Bell states, as mentioned in subsection 2.2.2, provide much increase in fidelity in Repetition codes. An extension (or generalization) of Bell states is the Greenberger-Horne-Zeilinger state or GHZ

²⁵Here $H(S)$ means the information or entropy of a system S . H does not indicate a Hermitian operator here and this is the only exception

state.

Fidelity is defined as the probability of decoding a qubit as itself after it travels through a channel. Mathematically,

$$F(\rho, |\phi\rangle) = \sqrt{\langle\phi|\rho|\phi\rangle} \quad (2.57)$$

where ρ is the mixed state density matrix of the decoded received qubit coming through the channel and $|\phi\rangle$ is the actual transmitted qubit. It is used as a measure of the efficacy of any Quantum Error Correction Code in correcting errors in decoded qubits.

Chapter 3

Introduction to Quantum Error Correction

Chapter 2 describes the necessary theoretical aspects of Quantum Communication. This chapter first introduces the GHZ state, and then discusses the Quantum Error Correction (QEC) codes. The general Quantum Repetition Codes (QRC) along with the encoder-decoder schemes and performance evaluation of traditional 3-bit and 5-bit QRC codes are then discussed.

3.1 GHZ state

The **GHZ (Greenberger-Horne-Zeilinger) state** is a specific type of entangled quantum state involving three or more qubits. It is named after the physicists who introduced it [16]. For a three-qubit system, the GHZ state is typically written as [50]:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|000\rangle + |111\rangle) \quad (3.1)$$

This state exhibits maximal entanglement, which means that the qubits are strongly correlated so that the outcome of the measurement of any one qubit determines the states of the others.

The **GHZ state** is an entangled quantum state that involves $M > 2$ subsystems. If each subsystem has dimension d , i.e. the local Hilbert space is isomorphic to \mathbb{C}^d , then the total Hilbert space of an M -partite system is given by:

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{tot}} = (\mathbb{C}^d)^{\otimes M} \quad (3.2)$$

This state is often referred to as an M -partite qudit GHZ state [51]. The general formula for

this state is:

$$\begin{aligned} |\text{GHZ}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}} \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} |i\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |i\rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}} (|0\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |0\rangle + \cdots + |d-1\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |d-1\rangle) \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

For the special case where each subsystem is two-dimensional (i.e., a collection of M qubits), the state simplifies to:

$$|\text{GHZ}\rangle = \frac{|0\rangle^{\otimes M} + |1\rangle^{\otimes M}}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (3.4)$$

When the probabilities associated with each separate state in the entangled state are not equal, they are referred to as **Generalized GHZ states**.

$$|\text{GHZ}\rangle_{\text{generalized}} = a|0\rangle^{\otimes M} + b|1\rangle^{\otimes M}. \quad (3.5)$$

where $a^2 + b^2 = 1$.

3.2 Quantum Error Correcting (QEC) Codes

Quantum Error Correction (QEC) codes operate through a three-step process: **error detection**, **error identification** and **error correction**. Every QEC circuit must include these three components as shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: A basic quantum error-correcting scheme¹

After preparing the logical state $|\psi\rangle_L$, we proceed to error detection. In most QEC schemes, **stabilizer codes** are used for this purpose. Stabilizer codes work by checking the parity of two or more qubits using CNOT gates. The output of these stabilizers, known as **syndrome bits**, indicates whether an error has occurred. The syndrome bit takes the value $+1$ for an error-free case and -1 for an erroneous case.

¹This figure is taken from [52].

Error detection relies on syndrome bits to identify the location of the error. Once the error position is known, correction becomes straightforward. Since Pauli gates are self-inverse or involutory, applying a Pauli gate twice restores the original state. Therefore, once the location of the error is determined, the correction process simply involves reapplying the appropriate gate to the affected qubit.

For illustration, consider a 3-qubit encoded state $|\psi\rangle_l$ that undergoes a single bit-flip error e , represented as:

$$e = X \otimes I \otimes I. \quad (3.6)$$

To correct for this error, we apply a correction operator c , such that:

$$ce|\psi\rangle_l = |\psi\rangle_l. \quad (3.7)$$

Since Pauli gates satisfy the self-inverse property [53], the correction is valid when:

$$c = e. \quad (3.8)$$

The following equation demonstrates how the correction operator transforms the erroneous state back to the correct logical state [54].

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi\rangle_l \xrightarrow{\text{error}} e|\psi\rangle_l &= (X \otimes I \otimes I)|\psi\rangle_l \\ &= \alpha|100\rangle + \beta|011\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (3.9a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} e|\psi\rangle_l \xrightarrow{\text{correction}} ec|\psi\rangle_l &= (X \otimes I \otimes I)(X \otimes I \otimes I)|\psi\rangle_l \\ &= \alpha|000\rangle + \beta|111\rangle = |\psi\rangle_l \end{aligned} \quad (3.9b)$$

3.2.1 Performance Evaluation

A crucial aspect of designing error-correcting systems is evaluating their performance. One key performance metric is **the probability of error**. In quantum systems, this probability is intuitively understood as the maximum likelihood of obtaining an incorrect measurement outcome compared to the expected result.

To quantify this error, one compares the system's output state $|\psi_o\rangle$ with the input state $|\psi\rangle$. An upper bound on the error can be established by expressing the output state as a linear combina-

tion of the input state and an "error" state. Since quantum states combine through superposition, we can write:

$$|\psi_o\rangle = \gamma|\psi\rangle + |e\rangle. \quad (3.10)$$

The probability of error is then bounded by

$$\epsilon = \||e\rangle\|^2. \quad (3.11)$$

which is referred to as the "**error estimate**."

In general, there are multiple ways to decompose the output into an acceptable state and an error term. The goal is to choose the decomposition that minimizes the error estimate. The resulting value of ϵ allows us to define the **fidelity** as [17]:

$$F = \sqrt{1 - \epsilon}. \quad (3.12)$$

A fidelity of 1 indicates that the output state is identical to the input state, up to an overall phase factor.

3.3 Quantum Repetition Code (QRC)

The repetition code can be employed to safeguard quantum information when errors occur under a restricted model [23]. Consider a physical system composed of three qubits, where each qubit independently undergoes a bit-flip error, represented by the operator σ_x , with a probability of 0.25.

Using the superposition principle, the classical repetition code can be adapted to a quantum code, as quantum states cannot be duplicated similarly to classical information due to the no-cloning theorem [14]. The encoding of a single qubit follows the transformation:

$$\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle \rightarrow \alpha|000\rangle + \beta|111\rangle. \quad (3.13)$$

The quantum code corresponds to the two-dimensional subspace spanned by the basis states $|000\rangle$ and $|111\rangle$ [55]. This is a generalized GHZ state.

We assume the following properties: noise affects each qubit independently. For any given qubit, the noise leaves its state unchanged with probability $1 - p$ or applies a Pauli σ_x operator with probability p , where $p < \frac{1}{2}$. Although this model represents a highly idealized form of

noise, successfully correcting it will demonstrate that our error correction method can also be effective against more realistic noise models. However, QRC can also be used in phase-flip channel errors resembling a Pauli σ_z operator, but not in a mixed channel with both bit-flip and phase-flip errors.

Similarly to the classical case, decoding relies on majority voting. However, care must be taken to preserve quantum coherence while retrieving the stored information. This can be achieved by implementing only unitary operations to transfer the encoded information to the output qubit [21].

To illustrate error analysis, we compute the error probability for the repetition code applied to two different initial states: $|0\rangle$ and $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$.

For the initial state $|0\rangle$, the encoding follows:

$$|0\rangle \xrightarrow{\text{encode}} |000\rangle \quad (3.14)$$

After the error process, the state evolves into a mixture with the following probabilities:

$$|000\rangle \xrightarrow{\text{error}} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.75^3 : |000\rangle, \\ 0.25 \times 0.75^2 : |100\rangle, \\ 0.25 \times 0.75^2 : |010\rangle, \\ 0.25 \times 0.75^2 : |001\rangle, \\ 0.25^2 \times 0.75 : |110\rangle, \\ 0.25^2 \times 0.75 : |101\rangle, \\ 0.25^2 \times 0.75 : |011\rangle, \\ 0.25^3 : |111\rangle. \end{array} \right. \xrightarrow{\text{decode}} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.4219 : |00\rangle|0\rangle, \\ 0.1406 : |10\rangle|0\rangle, \\ 0.1406 : |01\rangle|0\rangle, \\ 0.1406 : |11\rangle|0\rangle, \\ 0.0469 : |11\rangle|1\rangle, \\ 0.0469 : |01\rangle|1\rangle, \\ 0.0469 : |10\rangle|1\rangle, \\ 0.0156 : |00\rangle|1\rangle. \end{array} \right. \quad (3.15)$$

The final state consists of a mixture of four correctly decoded and four incorrectly decoded components. The probability associated with each state is shown before the colon. The incorrectly decoded states are orthogonal to the encoded information and collectively have a probability of **0.1563**, which is an improvement over the single-qubit error probability of **0.25**.

For the second initial state $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle) \xrightarrow{\text{encode}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|000\rangle + |111\rangle) \quad (3.16a)$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|000\rangle + |111\rangle) \xrightarrow{\text{error}} \left\{ 0.25^2 \times 0.75 : \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|110\rangle + |001\rangle) \right\} \quad (3.16b)$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|110\rangle + |001\rangle) \xrightarrow{\text{decode}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|11\rangle(|1\rangle + |0\rangle) \quad (3.16c)$$

Although not all error events are explicitly listed, in each case, the state is decoded correctly, leading to an overall error probability of zero. This demonstrates that the probability of error can vary significantly depending on the initial state, especially the superposition of symmetric states with equal probabilities [17]. We will also show in our proposed error correction scheme that it can handle such states with 100% fidelity.

To detect this type of error, we can use a measurement called the **syndrome measurement**. A syndrome is a measurement that produces a number indicating the type of error. For a single bit-flip error, there are four possible scenarios:

1. No error occurred.
2. The first bit was flipped.
3. The second bit was flipped.
4. The third bit was flipped.

To associate a number with these four possibilities, we perform two measurements, each of which gives a result of 0 or 1. The possible outcomes of these measurements are 00, 01, 10, and 11, corresponding to the four potential errors. A circuit that implements this procedure is shown in Figure 3.2.

The transformation performed by the syndrome extraction circuit is represented by:

$$U_{\text{BF}} : |x_0, x_1, x_2, 0, 0\rangle \xrightarrow{\text{measure}} |x_0, x_1, x_2, x_0 + x_1, x_0 + x_2\rangle. \quad (3.17)$$

The bottom two bits in the figure are the **ancilla bits**, which assist in the computation. We refer to these as a_1 and a_2 . The additions are modulo 2 or can also be interpreted as two-bit XOR.

We begin with the initial state $a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle$, which is encoded as $a|000\rangle + b|111\rangle$.

The error detection circuit, along with the correction circuit, is shown in Figure 3.3.

The correction transformation is given by:

²Table 3.1 was taken from [56].

Figure 3.2: Detecting errors for the 3-bit bit-flip error correction code. The bottom two ancilla bits are measured to detect a single bit-flip error in the top three bits. The circuit is called a **syndrome extraction circuit**.

Table 3.1: Syndrome computation table for a Bit-flip Error (Figure 3.3)²

Error	State bits $ x_0x_1x_2\rangle$	Ancilla qubits $ a_1a_2\rangle$	Syndrome a_1a_2	Desired correction
None	$a 000\rangle + b 111\rangle$	$ 00\rangle$	00	none
$\mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{X}$	$a 001\rangle + b 110\rangle$	$ 01\rangle$	01	flip x_2
$\mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{X} \otimes \mathbf{I}$	$a 010\rangle + b 101\rangle$	$ 10\rangle$	10	flip x_1
$\mathbf{X} \otimes \mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{I}$	$a 100\rangle + b 011\rangle$	$ 11\rangle$	11	flip x_0

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_{\text{BFcorr}} = & \text{CNOT}(\text{control} = a_1 \wedge \bar{a}_2; \text{target} = x_2) \\
 & + \text{CNOT}(\text{control} = \bar{a}_1 \wedge a_2; \text{target} = x_1) \\
 & + \text{CNOT}(\text{control} = a_1 \wedge a_2; \text{target} = x_0).
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.18}$$

In this correction process, the control qubits are a_1 and a_2 , and the targets are the qubits x_0 , x_1 , and x_2 .

3.4 Three bit QRC

Consider a qubit that we want to protect, initially given by the state —

$$|\psi_1\rangle = a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle. \tag{3.19}$$

Figure 3.3: 3-bit QRC on a single state

After encoding this single qubit into three qubits [7], the resulting state becomes —

$$|\psi_3\rangle = a|000\rangle + b|111\rangle. \quad (3.20)$$

When two ancilla bits are added to this system, the initial state of the system is —

$$|\psi_5\rangle = (a|000\rangle + b|111\rangle) \otimes |00\rangle. \quad (3.21)$$

If a bit-flip error occurs on the third qubit, the state transforms into:

$$I \otimes I \otimes X \otimes I \otimes I |\psi_5\rangle = (a|001\rangle + b|110\rangle)|00\rangle. \quad (3.22)$$

Next, we pass this state through the error detection circuit. Since the second and third qubits differ in both superposition terms, the first ancilla bit becomes 1. Similarly, the first and third qubits also differ. So, the second ancilla bit also becomes 1. Before measurement, the new state is:

$$U_{\text{BF}}(I \otimes I \otimes X \otimes I \otimes I)|\psi_5\rangle = (a|001\rangle + b|110\rangle)|01\rangle. \quad (3.23)$$

Here, U_{BF} represents the error detection operation defined in Equation 3.17. Measurement of ancillary qubits gives the syndrome 01, indicating an error in the third qubit. The correction process applies an X (bit-flip) operation to the third qubit. After applying the correction, the final state is -

$$U_{\text{BFcorr}}U_{\text{BF}}(I \otimes I \otimes X \otimes I \otimes I)|\psi_5\rangle = (a|000\rangle + b|111\rangle)|11\rangle. \quad (3.24)$$

where the correction operation U_{BFcorr} is defined in Equation 3.18. We can observe that the first three qubits are successfully restored to their original state as in Equation 3.20.

3.4.1 Using the Extra State bits in Syndrome Measurement

We can even shorten our circuit by using the extra state bits in measuring the syndrome [57] [38]. After going through a single bit-flip error in the channel, we need not to measure syndrome. Rather, we can break the entanglement between our target qubit and the extra qubits and see what the states look like. Table 3.2 shows the syndrome calculation for bit flip error.

From the syndrome computation Table 3.2, we can see that three of the four cases do not demand correction on the target qubit. Only bit-flip on the target qubit needs a correction in this case. Therefore, this is a simplified convenient scheme for our purpose of 3-bit QRC on a single state. Figure 3.4 shows the 3-bit QRC encoder-channel-decoder circuit without ancillary bits.

Table 3.2: Syndrome computation table for a Bit-flip Error (Figure 3.4)

error	State bits after breaking entanglement $ x_0x_1x_2\rangle$	ancillary qubits $ x_1x_2\rangle$	syndrome x_1x_2	desired correction
None	$(a 0\rangle + b 1\rangle) \otimes 00\rangle$	$ 00\rangle$	00	none
$I \otimes I \otimes X$	$(a 0\rangle + b 1\rangle) \otimes 01\rangle$	$ 01\rangle$	01	none
$I \otimes X \otimes I$	$(a 0\rangle + b 1\rangle) \otimes 10\rangle$	$ 10\rangle$	10	none
$X \otimes I \otimes I$	$(a 1\rangle + b 0\rangle) \otimes 11\rangle$	$ 11\rangle$	11	flip x_0

Figure 3.4: 3-bit QRC on a single state without extra ancillary bits

3.4.2 Correcting Phase Flip Errors

The three-bit error correction scheme can also be designed to correct for phase-flip errors. In this case, we encode —

$$|0\rangle \rightarrow |+++ \rangle \tag{3.25a}$$

$$|1\rangle \rightarrow |-- \rangle \tag{3.25b}$$

Here $|+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$ and $|-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - |1\rangle)$. Figure 3.5 shows the corresponding encoder circuit.

Figure 3.5: Encoding circuit for the 3-bit phase flip error code

A sign (or phase) error in a single bit is described by the Pauli- Z gate – $Z|0\rangle = |0\rangle$ and $Z|1\rangle = -|1\rangle$. The Pauli Z gate swaps the $|+\rangle, |-\rangle$ states. The Hadamard gate H transfers from the $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$ basis to the $\{|+\rangle, |-\rangle\}$ basis.

Performing phase errors on single bits —

$$\mathbf{Z}_1|+++ \rangle = |-++ \rangle, \mathbf{Z}_1|--- \rangle = |+-- \rangle \quad (3.26a)$$

$$\mathbf{Z}_2|+++ \rangle = |+-+ \rangle, \mathbf{Z}_2|--- \rangle = |-+- \rangle \quad (3.26b)$$

$$\mathbf{Z}_3|+++ \rangle = |++- \rangle, \mathbf{Z}_3|--- \rangle = |--+ \rangle \quad (3.26c)$$

After going through the channel, we can easily convert these states into corresponding bit-flip states by applying Hadamard gate H again.

$$|-++ \rangle \xrightarrow{H} |100\rangle, |+-- \rangle \xrightarrow{H} |011\rangle \quad (3.27a)$$

$$|+-+ \rangle \xrightarrow{H} |010\rangle, |-+- \rangle \xrightarrow{H} |101\rangle \quad (3.27b)$$

$$|++- \rangle \xrightarrow{H} |001\rangle, |--+ \rangle \xrightarrow{H} |110\rangle \quad (3.27c)$$

As we have translated the phase-flip states into the bit-flip states, the rest of the scheme is the same as shown in Figure 3.3 or the simplified version in 3.4.

3.4.3 Fidelity Calculation

Let us assume that the probability of bit-flip is given by p and the number of corrected states for i bit-flips is a_i . The probabilities and corrected states are given in Table 3.3.

In this case, the theoretical fidelity—

Table 3.3: Performance of the 3-bit QRC

No of Bit flips	Probability	Total States	Corrected States, a_i
0	$(1 - p)^3$	1	1
1	$p(1 - p)^2$	3	3
2	$p^2(1 - p)$	3	0
3	p^3	1	0
Total		$2^3 = 8$	4

$$F = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^3 a_i p^i (1 - p)^{3-i}} \tag{3.28}$$

3.5 Five bit QRC

Using the extra four state bits as ancillary bits, here is how the simplified five-bit QRC scheme would look as shown in Figure 3.6:

Figure 3.6: 5-bit QRC on a single state

Table 3.4 is constructed following the same procedure as in Table 3.3.

Table 3.4: Performance of the 5-qubit repetition code³

No of Bit flips	Probability	Total States	Corrected States, a_i
0	$(1 - p)^5$	1	1
1	$p(1 - p)^4$	5	5
2	$p^2(1 - p)^3$	10	10
3	$p^3(1 - p)^2$	10	0
4	$p^4(1 - p)^1$	5	0
5	p^5	1	0
Total		$2^5 = 32$	16

For 5-bit QRC, the theoretical fidelity can be calculated using Equation 3.29—

$$F = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^5 a_i p^i (1-p)^{5-i}} \quad (3.29)$$

3.5.1 Comparison with the 3-bit QRC

There is a significant improvement in fidelity in raising from 3-bit to 5-bit QRC (refer to Figure 3.7 shown later). The factors involved are **fully handling capacity** and **number of corrected cases**.

The 3-bit QRC can only handle less than two bit-flips (or phase-flips in a channel with phase errors) completely. 5-bit QRC has the upper hand in this case as it can handle at most two bit-flips.

By comparing Table 3.3 with Table 3.4, we can notice that the number of corrected cases for the 5-bit QRC is much greater than that for the 3-bit QRC. This discrepancy significantly increases theoretical fidelity as the number of corrected states a_i is a major parameter in Equations 3.28 and 3.29.

3.6 Performance Analysis of QRC

If no error correcting scheme is applied on a single qubit, the probability of getting correct bit would be $1 - p$. Therefore, the theoretical fidelity of an unprotected qubit would be [10]:

$$F = \sqrt{1 - p} \quad (3.30)$$

Let us see how the Quantum Repetition Codes have improved in correcting bit flip errors of a single qubit by plotting Equations 3.28-3.30 as shown in Figure 3.7.

³Table 3.3 and 3.4 were taken from [37].

Figure 3.7: Efficacy of Quantum Repetition Codes

From Figure 3.7, we can see that Quantum Repetition Codes are not effective for all noise probability. In low-noise channels ($p < 0.5$), QRC increases the fidelity i.e. protects the single qubit better. However, for high bit-flip noises ($p > 0.5$), the fidelity deteriorates.

The ineffectiveness of QRC in super noisy channels is due to the propagation of errors because of majority polling. Whenever two errors occur, QRC transmits this error to the other unaffected qubit.

We can think of a single qubit encoded with two other state bits where error correction has not been applied. In this case, if the two state bits get affected, our target qubit would still be protected.

$$\begin{aligned}
 a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle &\xrightarrow{\text{encode}} a|000\rangle + b|111\rangle \\
 &\xrightarrow{\mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{X} \otimes \mathbf{X}} a|011\rangle + b|100\rangle \\
 &\xrightarrow{\text{breaking entanglement}} (a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle) \otimes |11\rangle
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.31}$$

This is not the case in QRC as errors in the state bits would be spread to the target bit as well, which we can get an idea of which can be obtained from Table 3.2.

Chapter 4

Design and Simulation of the Proposed Extension of 3- and 5-bit QRC Codes

Chapter 4 describes the traditional encoder-decoder circuits for 3-bit and 5-bit Quantum Repetition Codes and also analyzes their performance. This chapter first describes the design and simulation procedure for quantum circuits. Then it introduces our proposed extension of the decoder scheme for 3-bit and 5-bit Quantum Repetition Codes on tri- and pentapartite GHZ states along with its simulation.

4.1 Design of Quantum Circuits

We designed Quantum circuits using **Qiskit**, an open-source software development kit developed by **IBM** [58]. It follows the circuit model for universal quantum computation, and can be used for any quantum hardware that follows this model [59]. The primary version of Qiskit uses the Python programming language.

We initialized quantum circuits using `QuantumCircuit()` in Qiskit. The number of qubits and classical bits was defined based on the problem requirements.

Then we implemented quantum operations to manipulate qubit states. This was done by adding various types of single-qubit and multi-qubit gates such as Hadamard, Pauli gates, and CNOT gate previously explained in Subsection 2.2.2.

Finally, qubits are measured to collapse their states and obtain classical outputs. To extract the results, we measure the qubits and map them to classical bits.

4.2 Simulation of Quantum Circuits

We have simulated quantum circuits using **Qiskit Aer**, which provides high-performance quantum computing simulators with realistic noise models [60] [61]. This provides simulators hosted locally on the user's device, as well as HPC resources available through the cloud.

We have used different types of simulations depending on the requirements of our quantum circuits:

- **Statevector Simulation:** We have used `statevector_simulator` to compute the exact quantum state of circuits, providing full wavefunction representation.
- **Shot-based QASM Simulation:** We have performed probabilistic simulations using `qasm_simulator`, which mimics real quantum hardware by returning measurement counts over multiple runs.
- **Noise-Aware Simulations:** We have incorporated realistic noise models using `AerSimulator` to study the impact of decoherence and gate errors on circuit performance.
- **Density Matrix Simulation:** We have used `aer_simulator_density_matrix` to model open quantum systems and track mixed-state evolution.
- **Matrix Product State (MPS) Simulation:** Enabling simulations of circuits with up to hundreds of qubits using `AerSimulator`.

4.3 Extension of Three-bit QRC on Tripartite GHZ State

We have designed 3-bit QRC scheme for a special case of the tripartite state, namely **Generalized GHZ state** for $M = 3$ system. Therefore, we are applying 3-bit QRC on each qubit which makes it a 9-bit code like Shor's Code [15]. However, this code accounts for bit-flip or phase-flip errors separately. It's particularly useful for GHZ state as it can be corrected in all cases, i.e. fidelity for **ideal GHZ state** is always one. Moreover, this code also shows higher fidelity than normal 3-bit QRC in low-noise channels for generalized GHZ states.

4.3.1 Decoding Circuit

We could have used a traditional decoding circuit as shown in Figure 3.2 or 3.4 in case of the Generalized GHZ states. That would have done the trick for increasing fidelity of these states than traditional 3-bit QRC.

But our intention was to make a full-proof error detection and correction circuit, particularly for the ideal GHZ state. Figure 4.1 shows the Syndrome Extraction and Correction Circuit for the tripartite GHZ state.

Figure 4.1: Syndrome Extraction and Correction Circuit for tripartite GHZ state

We name the target qubit **Alice** and other state qubits as **Bob** and **Eve**. After going through each bit’s separate 3-bit QRC scheme, we break the entanglement between each of them with respect to Alice. Then we store the syndrome of Bob and Eve in an ancillary qubit as shown in Table 3.3. Then we build the entanglement again and move on to Bob with the same process.

In traditional methods, we just wanted to correct Alice. But in this case, we would apply majority polling on each of the state qubits. If errors occur, then these would get transferred to the remaining as the majority voting.

In case of an ideal GHZ state, we can see it’s an entanglement between two completely orthogonal states with equal probabilities. Therefore, if each state adopts the erroneous bit, the result would be the same input bits, i.e. the ideal GHZ state would be corrected precisely.

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|000\rangle + |111\rangle) \xrightarrow{\text{Errors not corrected}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|110\rangle + |001\rangle) \xrightarrow{\text{Majority Polling}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|111\rangle + |000\rangle) \quad (4.1)$$

4.3.2 Design of the Complete Circuit

Figure 4.2 represents the complete design of a 3-bit RRC on a tripartite generalized GHZ state.

Figure 4.2: 3-bit QRC on a tripartite generalized GHZ state (the bottom part is the continuation of the first part to the right)

4.4 Extension of Five-bit QRC on Tripartite GHZ State

In this case, a 5-bit QRC encoding has been applied to Alice, Bob, and Eve before sending them off into the channel. Therefore, a total of 15 qubits are in this scheme. This encoder scheme is the same as the encoder shown in Figure 3.6, but here it is applied on each of the Alice, Bob and Eve qubits.

After separate 5-bit QRC implementation on each qubit, the 3-bit extended decoding circuit is similar to the one shown in Figure 4.1. Figure 4.3 shows the complete design of a 5-bit QRC on a tripartite generalized GHZ state.

Figure 4.3: 5-bit QRC on a tripartite generalized GHZ state (the bottom part is the continuation of the first part to the right)

4.5 Extension of Three-bit QRC on Pentapartite GHZ State

In pentapartite ($M = 5$) state, we name the target qubit **Alice** as before. And the other state qubits are named as **Bob**, **Eve**, **Charlie**, and **Dave** respectively. Total number of qubits is 15, the same as in the previous case.

Before entering into the channel, each of the state qubits undergoes separate 3-bit QRC encoding. Then each qubit is separately corrected as shown in Figure 3.6.

4.5.1 The Decoding Circuit

Similar to the tripartite GHZ counterpart, this circuit works by freeing the entanglement between the five qubits, stores the syndrome on an ancillary bit, and then turns on the entanglement again. The syndrome storing idea is same the one as shown in Figure 3.6.

It should be noted here that this complexity in the circuit is added solely for the guaranteed protection of the pentapartite ideal GHZ state. Otherwise, following the same scheme as in Figure 3.6, would result in the same fidelity for any generalized GHZ state. Figure 4.4 shows the syndrome extraction and correction circuit for the pentapartite generalized GHZ state.

Figure 4.4: Syndrome Extraction and Correction Circuit for pentapartite generalized GHZ state (each subsequent part after the first is the continuation of the first part to the right)

4.5.2 Design of the Complete Circuit

The complete circuit is formed when both the encoder and decoders are connected together with the channel in between, as presented in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5: 3-bit QRC on a pentapartite generalized GHZ state (each subsequent part after the first is the continuation of the first part to the right)

4.6 Extension of Five-bit QRC on Pentapartite GHZ State

Here, a 5-bit QRC is applied to each of the state qubits - Alice, Bob, Eve, Charlie and Dave. This has the highest number of Qubits, 25 by count.

Afterwards, the decoding circuit will be same as the shown in Figure 4.4. Figure 4.6 shows the encoder-channel-decoder circuit for the 5-bit QRC on a pentapartite generalized GHZ state.

Figure 4.6: 5-bit QRC on a pentapartite generalized GHZ state (each subsequent part after the first is the continuation of the first part to the right)

Chapter 5

Results and Discussion

Chapter 4 presented the design and simulation of our proposed extension of the decoder schemes for 3-bit and 5-bit QRC on tri- and pentapartite GHZ states. Chapter 5 discusses the effectiveness and novelty of our proposed schemes by showing our acquired results. In the case of an Ideal GHZ state, we simulated our first proposed scheme i.e. extension of 3-bit QRC on a tripartite GHZ state, and checked if it matches with our theoretical prediction. In the case of generalized states, we calculated the theoretical fidelity of all our schemes and compared them against the traditional analogues.

5.1 Fidelity of an Ideal GHZ state

Since all of our proposed schemes are theoretically proven to protect GHZ state flawlessly, we checked the result of one of the schemes on an ideal GHZ state. We chose the easiest one, i.e. 3-bit QRC on tripartite GHZ state using 9 qubits.

5.1.1 Simulation Method

Since calculating the actual fidelity of a circuit containing nine qubits is computationally expensive, we tried to calculate the approximate fidelity using 'matrix_product_state' method in `AerSimulator` class from **Qiskit Aer** [61].

We created the bit-flip channel by applying Identity gates throughout the channel. Then a noise model is implemented by applying σ_x (Pauli-X) error with a rate p into these gates.

For each simulation, we ran for 300 shots in a local simulator named **AerSimulator** which supports noise models. We also ran the simulations 15 times for more accuracy. Then we averaged the count of shots where we obtained our desired state $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|000\rangle + |111\rangle)$ from the

Figure 5.1: Circuit Diagram for simulation of a 3-bit QRC on a tripartite ideal GHZ state

output. Approximate fidelity is then calculated by:

$$F_{approx} = \frac{\text{No. of shots with desired state as output}}{\text{Total No. of Shots}} \tag{5.1}$$

5.1.2 Simulation Results

The result of the simulation is plotted in Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2: Approximate Fidelity of a tripartite ideal GHZ state

We can see from Figure 5.2 that the simulation result matches perfectly with our theoretical calculation as shown in Equation 4.1. Therefore, it can be completely protected in all our proposed error correction schemes.

5.2 Fidelity of the Generalized GHZ States

Next, the fidelity of the generalized GHZ states are computed.

5.2.1 For Extended 3-bit QRC on Tripartite GHZ states

Table 5.1: Performance of the 3-bit QRC on tripartite GHZ states

No of Bit flips	Probability	Total States	Corrected States, a_i
0	$(1-p)^9$	1	1
1	$p(1-p)^8$	9	9
2	$p^2(1-p)^7$	$\binom{9}{2} = 36$	36
3	$p^3(1-p)^6$	$\binom{9}{3} = 84$	84
4	$p^4(1-p)^5$	$\binom{9}{4} = 126$	$\binom{9}{4} - \binom{3}{2} \cdot \binom{3}{2} \cdot \binom{3}{2} = 99$
5	$p^5(1-p)^4$	$\binom{9}{5} = 126$	$\binom{3}{3} \cdot \binom{3}{1}^2 \cdot 3 = 27$
6	$p^6(1-p)^3$	$\binom{9}{6} = 84$	0
7	$p^7(1-p)^2$	$\binom{9}{7} = 36$	0
8	$p^8(1-p)^1$	$\binom{9}{8} = 9$	0
9	p^9	1	0
Total		$2^9 = 512$	256

Let us assume that the bit-flip ratio is represented by p . In this case, the theoretical fidelity is given by,

$$F = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^9 a_i p^i (1-p)^{9-i}} \quad (5.2)$$

5.2.2 For an Extended 5-bit QRC on Tripartite GHZ states

Table 5.2: Performance of the 5-bit QRC on tripartite GHZ states

No of Bit flips	Probability	Total States	Corrected States, a_i
0	$(1-p)^{15}$	1	1
1	$p(1-p)^{14}$	15	15
2	$p^2(1-p)^{13}$	$\binom{15}{2} = 105$	105
3	$p^3(1-p)^{12}$	$\binom{15}{3} = 455$	455
4	$p^4(1-p)^{11}$	$\binom{15}{4} = 1365$	1365
5	$p^5(1-p)^{10}$	$\binom{15}{5} = 3003$	3003
6	$p^6(1-p)^9$	$\binom{15}{6} = 5005$	$\binom{15}{6} - \binom{3}{2} \cdot \binom{5}{3}^2 = 4705$
7	$p^7(1-p)^8$	$\binom{15}{7} = 6435$	$\binom{15}{7} - \binom{3}{2} \cdot \binom{5}{4} \cdot \binom{5}{3} \cdot 2! - \binom{5}{3}^2 \cdot \binom{5}{1} \cdot 3 = 4635$
8	$p^8(1-p)^7$	$\binom{15}{8} = 6435$	$\binom{5}{4} \cdot \binom{5}{2}^2 \cdot 3 + \binom{5}{5} \cdot \binom{5}{2} \cdot \binom{5}{1} \cdot 3! = 1800$
9	$p^9(1-p)^6$	$\binom{15}{9} = 5005$	$\binom{5}{5} \cdot \binom{5}{2}^2 \cdot 3 = 300$
10	$p^{10}(1-p)^5$	$\binom{15}{10} = 3003$	0
11	$p^{11}(1-p)^4$	$\binom{15}{11} = 1365$	0
12	$p^{12}(1-p)^3$	$\binom{15}{12} = 455$	0
13	$p^{13}(1-p)^2$	$\binom{15}{13} = 105$	0
14	$p^{14}(1-p)^1$	$\binom{15}{14} = 15$	0
15	p^{15}	1	0
Total		$2^{15} = 32768$	16384

In this case, the theoretical fidelity is given by,

$$F = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^{15} a_i p^i (1-p)^{15-i}} \quad (5.3)$$

5.2.3 For an Extended 3-bit QRC on Pentapartite GHZ states

Table 5.3: Performance of the 3-bit QRC on pentapartite GHZ states

No of Bit flips	Probability	Total States	Corrected States, a_i
0	$(1 - p)^{15}$	1	1
1	$p(1 - p)^{14}$	15	15
2	$p^2(1 - p)^{13}$	$\binom{15}{2} = 105$	105
3	$p^3(1 - p)^{12}$	$\binom{15}{3} = 455$	455
4	$p^4(1 - p)^{11}$	$\binom{15}{4} = 1365$	1365
5	$p^5(1 - p)^{10}$	$\binom{15}{5} = 3003$	3003
6	$p^6(1 - p)^9$	$\binom{15}{6} = 5005$	$\binom{15}{6} - \binom{5}{3} \cdot \binom{3}{2}^3 = 4735$
7	$p^7(1 - p)^8$	$\binom{15}{7} = 6435$	$\binom{15}{7} - \binom{5}{3} \cdot \binom{3}{2}^2 \cdot \binom{3}{3} \cdot 3 - \binom{5}{4} \cdot \binom{3}{2}^3 \cdot \binom{3}{1} \cdot 4 = 4545$
8	$p^8(1 - p)^7$	$\binom{15}{8} = 6435$	$\binom{3}{3} \cdot \binom{3}{2} \cdot \binom{3}{1}^3 \cdot \frac{5!}{3!} + \binom{5}{4} \cdot \binom{3}{3}^2 \cdot \binom{3}{1}^2 \cdot \frac{4!}{2! \cdot 2!} = 1890$
9	$p^9(1 - p)^6$	$\binom{15}{9} = 5005$	$\binom{3}{3}^2 \cdot \binom{3}{1}^3 \cdot \frac{5!}{2! \cdot 3!} = 270$
10	$p^{10}(1 - p)^5$	$\binom{15}{10} = 3003$	0
11	$p^{11}(1 - p)^4$	$\binom{15}{11} = 1365$	0
12	$p^{12}(1 - p)^3$	$\binom{15}{12} = 455$	0
13	$p^{13}(1 - p)^2$	$\binom{15}{13} = 105$	0
14	$p^{14}(1 - p)^1$	$\binom{15}{14} = 15$	0
15	p^{15}	1	0
Total		$2^{15} = 32768$	16384

In this case, the theoretical fidelity is given by,

$$F = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^{15} a_i p^i (1 - p)^{15-i}} \quad (5.4)$$

5.2.4 For an Extended 5-bit QRC on Pentapartite GHZ states

Table 5.4: Performance of the 5-bit QRC on pentapartite GHZ states

No of Bit flips	Probability	Total States	Corrected States, a_i
0	$(1 - p)^{25}$	1	1
1	$p(1 - p)^{24}$	25	25
2	$p^2(1 - p)^{23}$	$\binom{25}{2} = 300$	300
3	$p^3(1 - p)^{22}$	$\binom{25}{3} = 2300$	2300
4	$p^4(1 - p)^{21}$	$\binom{25}{4} = 12650$	12650
5	$p^5(1 - p)^{20}$	$\binom{25}{5} = 53130$	53130
6	$p^6(1 - p)^{19}$	$\binom{25}{6} = 177100$	177100
7	$p^7(1 - p)^{18}$	$\binom{25}{7} = 480700$	480700
8	$p^8(1 - p)^{17}$	$\binom{25}{8} = 1081575$	1081575
9	$p^9(1 - p)^{16}$	$\binom{25}{9} = 2042975$	2032975
10	$p^{10}(1 - p)^{15}$	$\binom{25}{10} = 3268760$	3153760
11	$p^{11}(1 - p)^{14}$	$\binom{25}{11} = 4457400$	3846900
12	$p^{12}(1 - p)^{13}$	$\binom{25}{12} = 5200300$	3366050
13	$p^{13}(1 - p)^{12}$	$\binom{25}{13} = 5200300$	1834250
14	$p^{14}(1 - p)^{11}$	$\binom{25}{14} = 4457400$	610500
15	$p^{15}(1 - p)^{10}$	$\binom{25}{15} = 3268760$	115000
16	$p^{16}(1 - p)^9$	$\binom{25}{16} = 2042975$	10000
17	$p^{17}(1 - p)^8$	$\binom{25}{17} = 1081575$	0
18	$p^{18}(1 - p)^7$	$\binom{25}{18} = 480700$	0
19	$p^{19}(1 - p)^6$	$\binom{25}{19} = 177100$	0
20	$p^{20}(1 - p)^5$	$\binom{25}{20} = 53130$	0
21	$p^{21}(1 - p)^4$	$\binom{25}{21} = 12650$	0
22	$p^{22}(1 - p)^3$	$\binom{25}{22} = 2300$	0
23	$p^{23}(1 - p)^2$	$\binom{25}{23} = 300$	0
24	$p^{24}(1 - p)^1$	$\binom{25}{24} = 25$	0
25	p^{25}	1	0
Total		$2^{25} = 33554432$	16777216

In this case, the theoretical fidelity is given by,

$$F = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^{25} a_i p^i (1-p)^{25-i}} \quad (5.5)$$

5.2.5 Comparison of Results

To compare the fidelity of our proposed schemes, we first consider four cases of conventional 3-bit and 5-bit QRC explained in Section 3.4 and 3.5 respectively.

Case-1: Arbitrary single state – $a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle$,

Case-2: Generalized Bell state – $a|00\rangle + b|11\rangle$,

Case-3: Tripartite Generalized GHZ state – $a|000\rangle + b|111\rangle$, and

Case-4: Pentapartite Generalized GHZ state – $a|00000\rangle + b|11111\rangle$.

Figure 5.3 shows the theoretical fidelity of conventional 3-bit QRC for subsystems $M = 1, 2, 3$ & 5.

Figure 5.3: Comparison of a traditional 3-bit QRC from single state to pentapartite GHZ state

Since we are implementing a 3-bit QRC on each qubit in a multipartite GHZ state, the probability of error increases because even one bit-flip can change the state. As we can see from Figure 5.3, a 3-bit QRC on pentapartite GHZ state has the lowest fidelity. Therefore, increasing the

number of qubits is not an effective idea for a traditional 3-bit QRC.

Figure 5.4 shows the theoretical fidelity of conventional 5-bit QRC for subsystems $M = 1, 2, 3$ & 5.

Figure 5.4: Comparison of a traditional 5-bit QRC from single state to pentapartite GHZ state

The same reasoning can be applied to a 5-bit QRC as well. However, we can see from Figure 5.4 that there are some overlaps between the $M = 2, 3, 5$ subsystems. Still, a 5-bit QRC on a single state wins by a great margin.

In order to compare the fidelity of our extended 3-bit QRC, we would take only the best case scenario of Figure 5.3, i.e. a 3-bit QRC on an arbitrary single state.

Figure 5.5 shows the theoretical fidelity of extended 3-bit QRC on tripartite and pentapartite generalized GHZ states with respect to traditional 3-bit QRC on a single state.

Figure 5.5: Comparison of an extended 3-bit QRC with best traditional scheme

We can see from $p = 0$ to $p = 0.5$ in Figure 5.5 that the proposed extended 3-bit QRC performs much better than the traditional 3-bit QRC. Despite the decrease in fidelity with respect to addition of qubit in the case of a traditional QRC as shown in Figure 5.3, we can observe quite an opposite trend in this case.

The reason for this is due to the difference in bit-flip handling capability of the schemes. In tripartite GHZ state, the scheme can handle less than four bit-flips without any casualty, whereas the handling capability is less than six bit-flips in a pentapartite scenario. Also, the number of corrected cases is greater in a pentapartite GHZ state.

However, for bit-flip probability greater than 0.5, a traditional 3-bit QRC is still the best scheme comparatively. We may recall from Section 3.6 that in channels with high noise, QRC is not constructive in protecting qubits. Therefore, it is not a very relevant drawback of our proposed scheme.

Figure 5.6 shows the comparison of theoretical fidelity between the extended 5-bit QRC on tripartite and pentapartite generalized GHZ states, and traditional 5-bit QRC on a single state.

Figure 5.6: Comparison of an extended 5-bit QRC with best traditional scheme

The result of an extended 5-bit QRC is similar to the previous case of Figure 5.5. In the case of low noise ($0 < p < 0.5$), our scheme safeguards the pentapartite GHZ state with the highest reliability. Again for higher noise ($0.5 < p < 1$), the traditional 5-bit QRC is still the best scheme out of the three.

Note that seamless handling capability on tripartite and pentapartite GHZ states are at most five bit-flips and eight bit-flips, respectively. Number of corrected cases is also higher on the pentapartite side.

Since Quantum Repetition Schemes are only applicable in the $p < 0.5$ region (refer to Section 3.6), comparison of all our schemes along with the traditional ones is relevant only in this region ($p < 0.5$).

Finally, Figure 5.7 shows the theoretical fidelity of all our proposed schemes along with traditional 3-bit and 5-bit QRC on a single state for $0 < p < 0.5$.

Figure 5.7: Comparison of all proposed schemes with traditional 3-bit and 5-bit QRC

As expected, an extended 5-bit QRC on pentapartite GHZ has the highest fidelity and has a margin of $0.075 - 0.1$ for $0.25 < p < 0.4$ over a traditional 3-bit QRC. In the same region, it has a maximum margin of 0.075 over a traditional 5-bit QRC.

Also, we cannot find the fidelity graph of extended 5-bit QRC on tripartite GHZ state, as it coincides completely with extended 3-bit on pentapartite GHZ. Note from our previous discussion that they both can handle less than six bit-flips flawlessly. The number of qubits and combination of corrected cases are also similar in both the schemes.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Future Work

This chapter first discusses the concluding remarks on our thesis work by summarizing our objectives and acquired results. Then it explains the novelty of our work and its contribution to the field of Quantum Error Correction. Lastly, it presents the future directions of our work.

6.1 Conclusions

Our proposed error-correction schemes are designed especially for the protection of ideal GHZ state. And they absolutely excel in this regard as shown for tripartite ideal GHZ state in Figure 5.2. The fidelity of tripartite and pentapartite ideal GHZ state will always be 100% in any type of bit-flip (or phase-flip with a slight modification) noisy channel for our schemes.

In case of generalized GHZ states, our schemes show remarkable fidelity than the conventional counterpart for low-noise channels ($p < 0.5$). This is completely okay considering the fact that QRCs have their own drawbacks in excessive noisy channels (Section 3.6). Our extended 5-bit QRC on pentapartite GHZ state shows fidelity margin of at most 0.075 and 0.1 over traditional 5-bit and 3-bit QRC respectively. In practical large-scale quantum computation, this increase in fidelity is highly significant where millions of qubits are used [24] [62].

6.2 Contributions and Novelty

The key novelty of our work lies in extending quantum repetition codes to tripartite and pentapartite GHZ states, ensuring enhanced error protection. Unlike conventional QRCs, which are typically applied to single qubits, our extended schemes utilize multi-qubit entanglement to achieve superior fidelity.

Additionally, our approach is highly efficient for low-noise environments. This makes it par-

ticularly valuable for early-stage quantum technologies where noise levels are still manageable. By demonstrating a reliable error-correction mechanism for GHZ states, we contribute to advancing fault-tolerant quantum computation and communication [9]. The results also provide a foundation for further improving quantum error correction methods, especially in entangled multi-qubit systems.

6.3 Suggestions for Future Work

Although 7-bit QRCs are not conventionally used, implementing such a scheme could be a promising direction for future research. If successfully applied to a generalized tripartite GHZ state, it may offer an error-correction solution with fewer qubits than our 5-bit QRC on pentapartite GHZ states.

However, the performance of a 7-bit QRC for GHZ state protection remains uncertain and requires further investigation. Given the observed trend that increasing qubits in QRC improves fidelity from Subsection 3.5.1, this approach could provide an optimized balance between qubit count and error tolerance. Exploring such schemes and testing their performance in different noise environments could be our future direction in quantum error correction.

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Appendix A

Codes

A.1 Design of Error-correcting Schemes

A.1.1 Extended 3-bit QRC on Tripartite GHZ state

```
1 from matplotlib.pyplot import *
2 from qiskit import QuantumCircuit
3 from qiskit import QuantumRegister, ClassicalRegister
4 from qiskit.quantum_info import Statevector
5
6 cr= ClassicalRegister(3, "measurement")
7 alice= QuantumRegister(1, 'alice__qubit')
8 bob= QuantumRegister(1, 'bob__qubit')
9 eve= QuantumRegister(1, 'eve__qubit')
10 aq1= QuantumRegister(2, 'ancilla_qubit_alice')
11 aq2= QuantumRegister(2, 'ancilla_qubit_bob')
12 aq3= QuantumRegister(2, 'ancilla_qubit_eve')
13 aq4= QuantumRegister(3, 'syndrome_ancilla')
14
15 threebit_triple = QuantumCircuit(alice, aq1, bob, aq2, eve, aq3, aq4, cr)
16
17 #threebit_triple.h(alice)
18 threebit_triple.cx(alice, bob)
19 threebit_triple.cx(alice, eve)
20
21 threebit_triple.barrier()
```

```
22 threebit_triple.cx(alice, aq1)
23 threebit_triple.cx(bob, aq2)
24 threebit_triple.cx(eve, aq3)
25
26 threebit_triple.barrier()
27
28 threebit_triple.x([2, 5, 8])
29 threebit_triple.barrier()
30
31 threebit_triple.cx(alice, aq1)
32 threebit_triple.cx(bob, aq2)
33 threebit_triple.cx(eve, aq3)
34
35 threebit_triple.mcx([1, 2], 0)
36 threebit_triple.mcx([4, 5], 3)
37 threebit_triple.mcx([7, 8], 6)
38 threebit_triple.barrier()
39
40 threebit_triple.cx(alice, eve)
41 threebit_triple.cx(alice, bob)
42 threebit_triple.ccx(bob, eve, aq4[0])
43 threebit_triple.cx(alice, eve)
44 threebit_triple.cx(alice, bob)
45 threebit_triple.barrier()
46
47 threebit_triple.cx(bob, alice)
48 threebit_triple.cx(bob, eve)
49 threebit_triple.ccx(alice, eve, aq4[1])
50 threebit_triple.cx(bob, alice)
51 threebit_triple.cx(bob, eve)
52 threebit_triple.barrier()
53
54 threebit_triple.cx(eve, alice)
55 threebit_triple.cx(eve, bob)
56 threebit_triple.ccx(alice, bob, aq4[2])
57 threebit_triple.cx(eve, alice)
58 threebit_triple.cx(eve, bob)
59 threebit_triple.barrier()
60
```

```

61
62 threebit_triple.cx(aq4[0],alice)
63 threebit_triple.cx(aq4[1],bob)
64 threebit_triple.cx(aq4[2],eve)
65 threebit_triple.cx(alice,eve)
66 threebit_triple.cx(alice,bob)
67 #threebit_triple.h(alice)
68 threebit_triple.barrier()
69
70 threebit_triple.measure([alice[0], bob[0], eve[0]],cr)
71 threebit_triple.draw(output='mpl')
72

```

A.1.2 Extended 5-bit QRC on Tripartite GHZ state

```

1  from matplotlib.pyplot import *
2  from qiskit import QuantumCircuit
3  from qiskit import QuantumRegister, ClassicalRegister
4  from qiskit.quantum_info import Statevector
5
6  cr= ClassicalRegister(3,"measurement")
7  alice= QuantumRegister(1, 'alice__qubit')
8  bob= QuantumRegister(1, 'bob__qubit')
9  eve= QuantumRegister(1, 'eve__qubit')
10 aq1= QuantumRegister(4, 'ancilla_qubit_alice')
11 aq2= QuantumRegister(4, 'ancilla_qubit_bob')
12 aq3= QuantumRegister(4, 'ancilla_qubit_eve')
13 aq4= QuantumRegister(3, 'syndrome_ancilla')
14
15 fivebit_triple = QuantumCircuit(alice,aq1,bob,aq2,eve,aq3,aq4,cr)
16
17 #fivebit_triple.h(alice)
18 fivebit_triple.cx(alice,bob)
19 fivebit_triple.cx(alice,eve)
20
21 fivebit_triple.barrier()
22 fivebit_triple.cx(alice, aq1)
23 fivebit_triple.cx(bob, aq2)

```

```
24 fivebit_triple.cx(eve, aq3)
25
26 fivebit_triple.barrier()
27
28 fivebit_triple.x([2,5,9,13])
29 fivebit_triple.barrier()
30
31 fivebit_triple.cx(alice, aq1)
32 fivebit_triple.cx(bob, aq2)
33 fivebit_triple.cx(eve, aq3)
34
35 fivebit_triple.mcx([1,2,3],0)
36 fivebit_triple.mcx([1,2,4],0)
37 fivebit_triple.mcx([1,3,4],0)
38 fivebit_triple.mcx([2,3,4],0)
39 fivebit_triple.mcx([1,2,3,4],0)
40 fivebit_triple.mcx([6,7,8],5)
41 fivebit_triple.mcx([6,7,9],5)
42 fivebit_triple.mcx([6,8,9],5)
43 fivebit_triple.mcx([7,8,9],5)
44 fivebit_triple.mcx([6,7,8,9],5)
45 fivebit_triple.mcx([11,12,13],10)
46 fivebit_triple.mcx([11,13,14],10)
47 fivebit_triple.mcx([11,13,14],10)
48 fivebit_triple.mcx([12,13,14],10)
49 fivebit_triple.mcx([11,12,13,14],10)
50 fivebit_triple.barrier()
51
52 fivebit_triple.cx(alice,eve)
53 fivebit_triple.cx(alice,bob)
54 fivebit_triple.ccx(bob, eve, aq4[0])
55 fivebit_triple.cx(alice,eve)
56 fivebit_triple.cx(alice,bob)
57 fivebit_triple.barrier()
58
59 fivebit_triple.cx(bob,alice)
60 fivebit_triple.cx(bob,eve)
61 fivebit_triple.ccx(alice, eve, aq4[1])
62 fivebit_triple.cx(bob,alice)
```

```

63 fivebit_triple.cx(bob,eve)
64 fivebit_triple.barrier()
65
66 fivebit_triple.cx(eve,alice)
67 fivebit_triple.cx(eve,bob)
68 fivebit_triple.ccx(alice, bob, aq4[2])
69 fivebit_triple.cx(eve,alice)
70 fivebit_triple.cx(eve,bob)
71 fivebit_triple.barrier()
72
73
74 fivebit_triple.cx(aq4[0],alice)
75 fivebit_triple.cx(aq4[1],bob)
76 fivebit_triple.cx(aq4[2],eve)
77 fivebit_triple.cx(alice,eve)
78 fivebit_triple.cx(alice,bob)
79 #fivebit_triple.h(alice)
80 fivebit_triple.barrier()
81
82 fivebit_triple.measure([alice[0], bob[0], eve[0]],cr)
83 fivebit_triple.draw(output='mpl')
84

```

A.1.3 Extended 3-bit QRC on Pentapartite GHZ state

```

1  from matplotlib.pyplot import *
2  from qiskit import QuantumCircuit
3  from qiskit import QuantumRegister, ClassicalRegister
4  from qiskit.quantum_info import Statevector
5
6  cr= ClassicalRegister(5,"measurement")
7  alice= QuantumRegister(1, 'alice__qubit')
8  bob= QuantumRegister(1, 'bob__qubit')
9  eve= QuantumRegister(1, 'eve__qubit')
10 charlie= QuantumRegister(1, 'charlie__qubit')
11 dave= QuantumRegister(1, 'dave__qubit')
12 aq1= QuantumRegister(2, 'ancilla_qubit_alice')
13 aq2= QuantumRegister(2, 'ancilla_qubit_bob')

```

```
14 aq3= QuantumRegister(2, 'ancilla_qubit_eve')
15 aq4= QuantumRegister(2, 'ancilla_qubit_charlie')
16 aq5= QuantumRegister(2, 'ancilla_qubit_dave')
17 aq6= QuantumRegister(5, 'syndrome_ancilla')
18
19 threebit_penta = QuantumCircuit(alice, aq1, bob, aq2, eve, aq3, charlie, aq4, dave)
20
21 #threebit_penta.h(alice)
22 threebit_penta.cx(alice, bob)
23 threebit_penta.cx(alice, eve)
24 threebit_penta.cx(alice, charlie)
25 threebit_penta.cx(alice, dave)
26
27 threebit_penta.barrier()
28 threebit_penta.cx(alice, aq1)
29 threebit_penta.cx(bob, aq2)
30 threebit_penta.cx(eve, aq3)
31 threebit_penta.cx(charlie, aq4)
32 threebit_penta.cx(dave, aq5)
33
34 threebit_penta.barrier()
35
36 threebit_penta.x([2, 5, 8, 13])
37 threebit_penta.barrier()
38
39 threebit_penta.cx(alice, aq1)
40 threebit_penta.cx(bob, aq2)
41 threebit_penta.cx(eve, aq3)
42 threebit_penta.cx(charlie, aq4)
43 threebit_penta.cx(dave, aq5)
44
45 threebit_penta.mcx([1, 2], 0)
46 threebit_penta.mcx([4, 5], 3)
47 threebit_penta.mcx([7, 8], 6)
48 threebit_penta.mcx([10, 11], 9)
49 threebit_penta.mcx([13, 14], 12)
50 threebit_penta.barrier()
51
52 threebit_penta.cx(alice, bob)
```

```
53 threebit_penta.cx(alice,eve)
54 threebit_penta.cx(alice,charlie)
55 threebit_penta.cx(alice,dave)
56 threebit_penta.mcx([bob, eve, charlie], aq6[0])
57 threebit_penta.mcx([bob, eve, dave], aq6[0])
58 threebit_penta.mcx([bob, dave, charlie], aq6[0])
59 threebit_penta.mcx([dave, eve, charlie], aq6[0])
60 threebit_penta.mcx([bob, eve, charlie, dave], aq6[0])
61 threebit_penta.cx(alice,bob)
62 threebit_penta.cx(alice,eve)
63 threebit_penta.cx(alice,charlie)
64 threebit_penta.cx(alice,dave)
65 threebit_penta.barrier()
66
67 threebit_penta.cx(bob,alice)
68 threebit_penta.cx(bob,eve)
69 threebit_penta.cx(bob,charlie)
70 threebit_penta.cx(bob,dave)
71 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, eve, charlie], aq6[1])
72 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, eve, dave], aq6[1])
73 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, charlie, dave], aq6[1])
74 threebit_penta.mcx([dave, eve, charlie], aq6[1])
75 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, eve, charlie,dave], aq6[1])
76 threebit_penta.cx(bob,alice)
77 threebit_penta.cx(bob,eve)
78 threebit_penta.cx(bob,charlie)
79 threebit_penta.cx(bob,dave)
80 threebit_penta.barrier()
81
82 threebit_penta.cx(eve,alice)
83 threebit_penta.cx(eve,bob)
84 threebit_penta.cx(eve,charlie)
85 threebit_penta.cx(eve,dave)
86 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, charlie], aq6[2])
87 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, dave], aq6[2])
88 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, dave, charlie], aq6[2])
89 threebit_penta.mcx([dave, bob, charlie], aq6[2])
90 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, charlie, dave], aq6[2])
91 threebit_penta.cx(eve,alice)
```

```
92 threebit_penta.cx(eve,bob)
93 threebit_penta.cx(eve,charlie)
94 threebit_penta.cx(eve,dave)
95 threebit_penta.barrier()
96
97 threebit_penta.cx(charlie,alice)
98 threebit_penta.cx(charlie,bob)
99 threebit_penta.cx(charlie,eve)
100 threebit_penta.cx(charlie,dave)
101 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, eve], aq6[3])
102 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, dave], aq6[3])
103 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, dave, eve], aq6[3])
104 threebit_penta.mcx([dave, bob, eve], aq6[3])
105 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, eve, dave], aq6[3])
106 threebit_penta.cx(charlie,alice)
107 threebit_penta.cx(charlie,bob)
108 threebit_penta.cx(charlie,eve)
109 threebit_penta.cx(charlie,dave)
110 threebit_penta.barrier()
111
112 threebit_penta.cx(dave,alice)
113 threebit_penta.cx(dave,bob)
114 threebit_penta.cx(dave,eve)
115 threebit_penta.cx(dave,charlie)
116 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, eve], aq6[4])
117 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, charlie], aq6[4])
118 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, charlie, eve], aq6[4])
119 threebit_penta.mcx([charlie, bob, eve], aq6[4])
120 threebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, eve, charlie], aq6[4])
121 threebit_penta.cx(dave,alice)
122 threebit_penta.cx(dave,bob)
123 threebit_penta.cx(dave,eve)
124 threebit_penta.cx(dave,charlie)
125 threebit_penta.barrier()
126
127 threebit_penta.cx(aq6[0],alice)
128 threebit_penta.cx(aq6[1],bob)
129 threebit_penta.cx(aq6[2],eve)
130 threebit_penta.cx(aq6[3],charlie)
```

```

131 threebit_penta.cx(aq6[4],dave)
132 threebit_penta.cx(alice,bob)
133 threebit_penta.cx(alice,eve)
134 threebit_penta.cx(alice,charlie)
135 threebit_penta.cx(alice,dave)
136 #threebit_penta.h(alice)
137 threebit_penta.barrier()
138
139 threebit_penta.measure([alice[0], bob[0], eve[0],charlie[0],dave[0]],cr)
140 threebit_penta.draw(output='mpl')
141

```

A.1.4 Extended 5-bit QRC on Pentapartite GHZ state

```

1  from matplotlib.pyplot import *
2  from qiskit import QuantumCircuit
3  from qiskit import QuantumRegister, ClassicalRegister
4  from qiskit.quantum_info import Statevector
5
6  cr= ClassicalRegister(5,"measurement")
7  alice= QuantumRegister(1, 'alice__qubit')
8  bob= QuantumRegister(1, 'bob__qubit')
9  eve= QuantumRegister(1, 'eve__qubit')
10 charlie= QuantumRegister(1, 'charlie__qubit')
11 dave= QuantumRegister(1, 'dave__qubit')
12 aq1= QuantumRegister(4, 'ancilla_qubit_alice')
13 aq2= QuantumRegister(4, 'ancilla_qubit_bob')
14 aq3= QuantumRegister(4, 'ancilla_qubit_eve')
15 aq4= QuantumRegister(4, 'ancilla_qubit_charlie')
16 aq5= QuantumRegister(4, 'ancilla_qubit_dave')
17 aq6= QuantumRegister(5, 'syndrome_ancilla')
18
19 fivebit_penta = QuantumCircuit(alice,aq1,bob,aq2,eve,aq3,charlie,aq4,dave)
20
21 #fivebit_penta.h(alice)
22 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,bob)
23 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,eve)
24 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,charlie)

```

```
25 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,dave)
26
27 fivebit_penta.barrier()
28 fivebit_penta.cx(alice, aq1)
29 fivebit_penta.cx(bob, aq2)
30 fivebit_penta.cx(eve, aq3)
31 fivebit_penta.cx(charlie, aq4)
32 fivebit_penta.cx(dave, aq5)
33
34 fivebit_penta.barrier()
35
36 fivebit_penta.x([2,5,9,15,21])
37 fivebit_penta.barrier()
38
39 fivebit_penta.cx(alice, aq1)
40 fivebit_penta.cx(bob, aq2)
41 fivebit_penta.cx(eve, aq3)
42 fivebit_penta.cx(charlie, aq4)
43 fivebit_penta.cx(dave, aq5)
44
45 fivebit_penta.mcx([1,2,3],0)
46 fivebit_penta.mcx([1,2,4],0)
47 fivebit_penta.mcx([1,3,4],0)
48 fivebit_penta.mcx([2,3,4],0)
49 fivebit_penta.mcx([1,2,3,4],0)
50 fivebit_penta.mcx([6,7,8],5)
51 fivebit_penta.mcx([6,7,9],5)
52 fivebit_penta.mcx([6,8,9],5)
53 fivebit_penta.mcx([7,8,9],5)
54 fivebit_penta.mcx([6,7,8,9],5)
55 fivebit_penta.mcx([11,12,13],10)
56 fivebit_penta.mcx([11,12,14],10)
57 fivebit_penta.mcx([11,13,14],10)
58 fivebit_penta.mcx([12,13,14],10)
59 fivebit_penta.mcx([11,12,13,14],10)
60 fivebit_penta.mcx([16,17,18],15)
61 fivebit_penta.mcx([16,17,19],15)
62 fivebit_penta.mcx([16,18,19],15)
63 fivebit_penta.mcx([17,18,19],15)
```

```
64 fivebit_penta.mcx([16,17,18,19],15)
65 fivebit_penta.mcx([21,22,23],20)
66 fivebit_penta.mcx([21,22,24],20)
67 fivebit_penta.mcx([21,23,24],20)
68 fivebit_penta.mcx([22,23,24],20)
69 fivebit_penta.mcx([21,22,23,24],20)
70 fivebit_penta.barrier()
71
72 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,bob)
73 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,eve)
74 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,charlie)
75 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,dave)
76 fivebit_penta.mcx([bob, eve, charlie], aq6[0])
77 fivebit_penta.mcx([bob, eve, dave], aq6[0])
78 fivebit_penta.mcx([bob, dave, charlie], aq6[0])
79 fivebit_penta.mcx([dave, eve, charlie], aq6[0])
80 fivebit_penta.mcx([bob, eve, charlie, dave], aq6[0])
81 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,bob)
82 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,eve)
83 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,charlie)
84 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,dave)
85 fivebit_penta.barrier()
86
87 fivebit_penta.cx(bob,alice)
88 fivebit_penta.cx(bob,eve)
89 fivebit_penta.cx(bob,charlie)
90 fivebit_penta.cx(bob,dave)
91 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, eve, charlie], aq6[1])
92 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, eve, dave], aq6[1])
93 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, charlie, dave], aq6[1])
94 fivebit_penta.mcx([dave, eve, charlie], aq6[1])
95 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, eve, charlie,dave], aq6[1])
96 fivebit_penta.cx(bob,alice)
97 fivebit_penta.cx(bob,eve)
98 fivebit_penta.cx(bob,charlie)
99 fivebit_penta.cx(bob,dave)
100 fivebit_penta.barrier()
101
102 fivebit_penta.cx(eve,alice)
```

```
103 fivebit_penta.cx(eve,bob)
104 fivebit_penta.cx(eve,charlie)
105 fivebit_penta.cx(eve,dave)
106 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, charlie], aq6[2])
107 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, dave], aq6[2])
108 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, dave, charlie], aq6[2])
109 fivebit_penta.mcx([dave, bob, charlie], aq6[2])
110 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, charlie, dave], aq6[2])
111 fivebit_penta.cx(eve,alice)
112 fivebit_penta.cx(eve,bob)
113 fivebit_penta.cx(eve,charlie)
114 fivebit_penta.cx(eve,dave)
115 fivebit_penta.barrier()
116
117 fivebit_penta.cx(charlie,alice)
118 fivebit_penta.cx(charlie,bob)
119 fivebit_penta.cx(charlie,eve)
120 fivebit_penta.cx(charlie,dave)
121 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, eve], aq6[3])
122 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, dave], aq6[3])
123 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, dave, eve], aq6[3])
124 fivebit_penta.mcx([dave, bob, eve], aq6[3])
125 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, eve, dave], aq6[3])
126 fivebit_penta.cx(charlie,alice)
127 fivebit_penta.cx(charlie,bob)
128 fivebit_penta.cx(charlie,eve)
129 fivebit_penta.cx(charlie,dave)
130 fivebit_penta.barrier()
131
132 fivebit_penta.cx(dave,alice)
133 fivebit_penta.cx(dave,bob)
134 fivebit_penta.cx(dave,eve)
135 fivebit_penta.cx(dave,charlie)
136 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, eve], aq6[4])
137 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, charlie], aq6[4])
138 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, charlie, eve], aq6[4])
139 fivebit_penta.mcx([charlie, bob, eve], aq6[4])
140 fivebit_penta.mcx([alice, bob, eve, charlie], aq6[4])
141 fivebit_penta.cx(dave,alice)
```

```

142 fivebit_penta.cx(dave,bob)
143 fivebit_penta.cx(dave,eve)
144 fivebit_penta.cx(dave,charlie)
145 fivebit_penta.barrier()
146
147 fivebit_penta.cx(aq6[0],alice)
148 fivebit_penta.cx(aq6[1],bob)
149 fivebit_penta.cx(aq6[2],eve)
150 fivebit_penta.cx(aq6[3],charlie)
151 fivebit_penta.cx(aq6[4],dave)
152 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,bob)
153 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,eve)
154 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,charlie)
155 fivebit_penta.cx(alice,dave)
156 #fivebit_penta.h(alice)
157 fivebit_penta.barrier()
158
159 fivebit_penta.measure([alice[0], bob[0], eve[0],charlie[0],dave[0]],cr)
160 fivebit_penta.draw(output='mpl')
161

```

A.2 Simulation of Extended 3-bit QRC on an Ideal Tripartite GHZ state

```

1 from numpy import *
2 from matplotlib.pyplot import *
3 from scipy.ndimage import gaussian_filter1d
4
5 # Importing standard Qiskit libraries
6 from qiskit import QuantumRegister, ClassicalRegister
7 from qiskit import QuantumCircuit, transpile, assemble
8 from qiskit_aer import Aer, noise, AerSimulator
9 from qiskit_aer.noise import depolarizing_error, NoiseModel, pauli_error
10 from qiskit.quantum_info import state_fidelity, Statevector, DensityMatrix
11
12 # from qiskit.tools.jupyter import *
13 from qiskit.visualization import *

```

```
14 from qiskit_ibm_runtime import QiskitRuntimeService
15
16 cr= ClassicalRegister(3, "bell_basis_measurement")
17 alice= QuantumRegister(1, 'alice__qubit')
18 bob= QuantumRegister(1, 'bob__qubit')
19 eve= QuantumRegister(1, 'eve__qubit')
20 aq1= QuantumRegister(2, 'ancilla_qubit_alice')
21 aq2= QuantumRegister(2, 'ancilla_qubit_bob')
22 aq3= QuantumRegister(2, 'ancilla_qubit_eve')
23 aq4= QuantumRegister(3, 'ancilla_reserve')
24
25 repetition3 = QuantumCircuit(alice, aq1, bob, aq2, eve, aq3, aq4, cr)
26
27 repetition3.h(alice)
28 repetition3.cx(alice, bob)
29 repetition3.cx(alice, eve)
30
31 repetition3.barrier()
32 repetition3.cx(alice, aq1)
33 repetition3.cx(bob, aq2)
34 repetition3.cx(eve, aq3)
35
36 repetition3.barrier()
37
38 repetition3.id(range(repetition3.num_qubits-3))
39 repetition3.barrier()
40
41 repetition3.cx(alice, aq1)
42 repetition3.cx(bob, aq2)
43 repetition3.cx(eve, aq3)
44
45 repetition3.mcx([1, 2], 0)
46 repetition3.mcx([4, 5], 3)
47 repetition3.mcx([7, 8], 6)
48 repetition3.barrier()
49
50 repetition3.cx(alice, eve)
51 repetition3.cx(alice, bob)
52 repetition3.ccx(bob, eve, aq4[0])
```

```
53 repetition3.cx(alice,eve)
54 repetition3.cx(alice,bob)
55 repetition3.barrier()
56
57 repetition3.cx(bob,alice)
58 repetition3.cx(bob,eve)
59 repetition3.ccx(alice, eve, aq4[1])
60 repetition3.cx(bob,alice)
61 repetition3.cx(bob,eve)
62 repetition3.barrier()
63
64 repetition3.cx(eve,alice)
65 repetition3.cx(eve,bob)
66 repetition3.ccx(alice, bob, aq4[2])
67 repetition3.cx(eve,alice)
68 repetition3.cx(eve,bob)
69 repetition3.barrier()
70
71
72 repetition3.cx(aq4[0],alice)
73 repetition3.cx(aq4[1],bob)
74 repetition3.cx(aq4[2],eve)
75 repetition3.cx(alice,eve)
76 repetition3.cx(alice,bob)
77 repetition3.h(alice)
78 repetition3.barrier()
79
80 repetition3.measure([alice[0], bob[0], eve[0]],cr)
81 repetition3.draw(output='mpl')
82
83 repetition3.draw(output='mpl').savefig("GHZ state simulation diagram.pdf")
84
85 # Range of noise levels for one-qubit gates
86 noise_prob = np.linspace(0,1,30)
87 # params = 4*noise_prob/3
88 fidelities3 = []
89
90 for rate in noise_prob:
91     # Create a new noise model with varying one-qubit depolarizing noise
```

```

92     noise_model = NoiseModel()
93     bit_flip_error = pauli_error([('X',rate), ('I', 1-rate)])
94
95     noise_model.add_all_qubit_quantum_error(bit_flip_error, 'id')
96
97     simulator = AerSimulator(method='matrix_product_state')
98     circuit = transpile(repetition3, simulator, optimization_level=0)
99
100     # Get and print the result
101     counts = simulator.run(circuit, noise_model=noise_model, shots=300).result()
102     for i in range(14):
103         count = simulator.run(circuit, noise_model=noise_model, shots=300).result()
104         counts = {key: count.get(key,0) + counts.get(key,0) for key in counts.keys()}
105
106     counts = {key: counts[key] / 15 for key in counts}
107     print(counts)
108     probabilities = {key: count / 300 for key, count in counts.items()}
109
110     # Calculate fidelity
111     fidelity = probabilities['000']
112     fidelities3.append(fidelity)
113
114     # Plot the fidelity graph
115     plot(noise_prob, gaussian_filter1d(fidelities3, sigma=1), marker='o')
116     xlabel('Bit flip rate in channel')
117     ylabel('Fidelity')
118     title('Fidelity vs. Bit flip Rate in a 3-bit QRC on a tripartite GHZ state')
119     ylim(0, 1.1)
120     grid()
121     legend()
122     savefig("Fidelity of GHZ state.pdf", dpi=400, bbox_inches="tight")

```

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**Performance Analysis of Extension of 3- and 5-bit
Quantum Repetition Codes**

**Masuk Ridwan Saunoo
Nafis Faisal**

**March
2025**
